

D2.5 Report on the Experts Meeting

(June 4-5 2018, RIVM, Bilthoven)

WP2 Integrative Strategic research Agenda

Responsible Partner: RIVM

Contributing partners: UCM, SSI, ISS, IP, Anses, BfR, SVA, INSA, UoS, WBVR, INIAV, AGES, NCE, FoHM, VISAVET-UCM, NDRVMI, INRA, NUIG, IISPV, VFL, INIA, Sciensano, PIWet, RKI, FLI, APHA, FHI, VRI, DTU, SLV, UTARTU, NIPH, NVI, IZSLER, PHE, IZSAM, TEAGASC

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Structure and objectives of the meeting

On the 4th and 5th of June 2018, an experts meeting was held at RIVM in Bilthoven, the Netherlands, to narrow down the previously identified research topics and to prioritize the narrowed down research as well as integrative topics. Input from this meeting will form the basis for defining the priority topics for the second internal call of project proposals and for updating the Strategic Research Agenda (SRA). The program of the meeting is in Appendix A.

Each OHEJP partner organization was invited to nominate a representative of their institute to participate in the meeting. This resulted in 37 experts¹ invited to attend the meeting, of which 36 effectively attended it (1 expert did not come). One expert could not attend the second day of the meeting. Seven Programme Management Team (PMT) members and 2 WP2 staff members also joined the meeting and acted as facilitators. The attendance list of the meeting is presented in Appendix B.

The first day of the meeting was dedicated to narrowing down the research topics following the presentation of the goals of the meeting and the preparatory work performed by WP5 (Science to policy translation), Task 2.2 of WP2 (Strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives), and the gap analysis of first round topics (Appendix F). The second day was dedicated to prioritizing the (narrowed down) research topics along with those stakeholders' needs that were not incorporated in the narrowed down topics, and to prioritize the integrative topics.

The procedures followed during the two days of the meeting are presented here below.

Procedures & outcomes

Narrow down procedure

For the narrow down procedure, experts were assigned to 1 of the 5 themes of in the OHEJP strategy matrix (see Appendix C). Each theme was recognizable by a color:

- **Analytical methods** (secretary: Stefano Morabito, ISS) → **RED**
- **Host-microbe interactions** (secretary: Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn, UCM) → **GREEN**
- **Epidemiology** (secretary: Dariusz Wasyl, PIWet) → **BLUE**
- **Risk assessment** (secretary: Maarten Nauta, DTU) → **YELLOW**
- **Intervention** (secretary: Merete Hofshagen, NVI) → **ORANGE**

As the theme secretary for host-microbe interactions, Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn, could not attend the meeting anymore, Karsten Nöckler kindly acted as substitute secretary. Except for the theme risk assessment in which there were relatively fewer experts, all other experts were assigned to 1 of 2 groups within their themes (Figure 1 and Appendix D). Subdivision of experts between groups was based on their expertise over the three OHEJP domains (foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance, and emerging threats), Med/Vet orientation of their

¹ Of the 41 OHEJP partners, 2 partners (MedVetNet Association and NCIPD were not eligible for attendance), 1 partner (INCDMIC) did not respond to the invitation, and the 2 Belgian partners (WIV-ISP and CODA-CERVA) merged in 1 institute (Sciensano), so they nominated only 1 expert.

institutes, and their countries of origin (to avoid having multiple experts from the same country in the same group). This last criterion also applied to the facilitators, to avoid having facilitators of the same nationality as the experts in the group. For the groups in which a secretary was present, no "fixed" facilitators were allocated, but only "free-roaming" facilitators (see Appendix D) who went around the different groups.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the subdivision of experts for the topics narrow down session.

Each expert was provided with a list of research topics and corresponding descriptions (exactly as reported in the current SRA) to be narrowed down by each theme. This list included the 12 topics prioritized in the first round but not selected for the first call, plus 4 topics that were selected for the first call but deemed insufficiently covered by the first round projects based on the gap analysis performed by the secretaries (Appendix F). Full descriptions of the 16 topics that were narrowed down is reported in Appendix E, while the report on the gap analysis presenting the rationale behind the re-consideration of the 4 previously selected topics, is reported in Appendix F.

The topics that were narrowed down were:

- **Analytical methods**
 - AMR-6: Metagenomics and bioinformatics for detection and surveillance of AMR pathogens and determinants
 - ET-1: Development and harmonisation of non-NGS-based methods for detection of FBZ agents and emerging threats
- **Host-microbe interactions**
 - FBZ-8: Model Systems (in vitro and in vivo) to study host/food – microbe interactions
 - ET-4: Host factors associated with colonization, persistence and disease
- **Epidemiology**
 - FBZ-4: Source attribution and transmission routes
 - FBZ-5: Epidemiological studies: risk factors and dynamics
 - AMR-2: Epidemiological studies into the dynamics of AMR in human and animals populations and the environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR

- ET-2: Improving preparedness and response
- ET-5: Ecology of emerging pathogens
- **Risk assessment**
 - FBZ-9: Frameworks and systems for sharing tools and data for risk assessment and effective decision making
 - AMR-5: Disease burden, socio-economic consequences and risk ranking
 - ET-3: Applying risk assessment/modelling methodologies to support decisions for the control of emerging threats, foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance
- **Intervention**
 - FBZ-3: Biosecurity and other interventions
 - FBZ-6: Risk communication and consumer targeted intervention strategies
 - FBZ-7: Optimizing options for risk management and enforcement in feed and food production and processing
 - AMR-4: Communication and Stewardship AMR

Each group within a theme was asked to narrow down the assigned topics independently of the other group, and to share/discuss each other outcomes with the other group at the end of the session. The theme secretary and the facilitators supported the work of both groups. Each group was asked to produce only 1 narrowed down topic per each original (broad) topic. This means that a maximum of 2 narrowed down topics (i.e. 1 per group) was produced for each original topic. An exception was made for the risk assessment theme as there was only 1 group herein; this group could produce up to 2 narrowed down topics for each broad topic. If two narrowed down topics happened to be the same or to overlap to a major extent with one another between the groups, then the two groups were asked to merge them as to provide only 1 narrowed down topic.

The original (broad) topic formed the basis to produce a more focused, i.e. narrowed down, topic. The experts did not necessarily have to write a completely new topic from scratch, but only to narrow down the existing ones. To narrow down the topics, the experts were asked to consult 4 sources of information, which provided guidance and input for producing more focused topics. These were:

1. **SOURCE I - National priorities** (Appendix G): visual representation in the form of word clouds, per broad topic, of the keywords extracted from all individual topics (which the broad topics were originally based upon) proposed by the OHEJP partners in 2016 and by newly joined partners prior to this experts meeting, reflecting the importance of specific aspects in the whole consortium.
2. **SOURCE II - European stakeholders' research needs**: tabulated summary of research needs expressed by EFSA, ECDC and DG SANTE (input provided by WP5, see Appendix H)
3. **SOURCE III - Gaps in the current work plan** (Appendix I): tabulated summary of research inputs needed to fill gaps in first round topics (extracted from the gap analysis of first round topics, see Appendix F)
4. **SOURCE IV - Other EU projects and initiatives** (Appendix L): inventory of other EU projects/initiatives and their description.

The first two sources summarized the research needs/interests of the countries/institutes participating in OHEJP and by the European stakeholders (EFSA, ECDC and DG SANTE). The other two sources described what are the current gaps in the work plan (gap analysis on the first round topics) and which are the other EU projects/initiatives with which the research produced within the narrowed down topics should ideally strategically interact (and not overlap) with. The format by which this information was presented was meant to facilitate its assessment, as this information has been placed in the OHEJP matrix to ease its identification when

narrowing down topics falling within specific research areas. The experts were invited to consider the information provided from these four sources as indications of the focus of the narrowed down topics linked to the respective research areas in the OHEJP matrix. The narrowed down topics had to reflect, as much as possible, the research needs in the OHEJP consortium and at the European level, to fill the gaps of the previous round, and to synergize with other EU projects and initiatives. The stakeholders' needs that were not incorporated into any narrowed down topic were taken into consideration as separate topics during the priority setting on day 2 of the meeting. Experts were reminded that the narrowed down topics did not necessarily have to include all the inputs provided, as this would have possibly resulted in even broader topics, and that the same input did not need to be included multiple times in different topics. The experts therefore had to refine the topic by giving more emphasis and focus on specific aspects by finding a compromise among the aforementioned 4 sources of information, distilling the key aspects so as to produce a balanced and more focused (narrowed down) topic. Subsequently, they were asked to make a short description of each new topic by using a standard format (topic description form, see Appendix M). Individual pathogens (e.g. *Salmonella*, HEV, *Toxoplasma*, etc.) were allowed to be specified in the narrowed down topics only if they were explicitly mentioned as such in one or more of the 4 sources of information provided. For all other circumstances, topics could not go further than the group level (e.g. foodborne viruses, soil-transmitted parasites, ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae, etc.). After the narrowing down session, the theme secretary briefly presented the narrowed down topics during the plenary session at the end of the day (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the narrowing down procedure.

Plenary presentation/discussion of narrowed-down topics (theme secretaries as rapporteurs)

Outcome of the narrow down session

Of the original 16 broad topics, the narrow down session resulted in a total of 19 narrowed down topics (9 for foodborne zoonoses, 4 for antimicrobial resistance, and 7 for emerging threats). The PMT then validated all these topics by performing an eligibility check with regard to the OHEJP scope. During this check, one topic originally included in the emerging threats domain was moved to the foodborne zoonoses one, as this topic fitted the other domain better. Moreover, as the description forms of some topics were not completed and a number of stakeholders' needs were to be included as separate topics (without descriptions) in this list, it was decided that the prioritization of the research topics had to be based on the topic titles only, as these titles were the least common denominator for all topics. This was done to avoid biasing the prioritization towards or away from certain topics for which descriptions were (un)available. To make sure that the topic titles were clear and included all essential information for the prioritization, the PMT further specified the titles of topics for which description forms were available by including pertinent information provided by the experts; titles were adjusted according to the rules for the narrow down procedure. The PMT also assessed which stakeholders' needs (as listed in Appendix N) were addressed in the narrowed down topics and which ones were left out and therefore needed to be considered as independent topics in the prioritization. The making of these additional topics based on the stakeholders' needs that were left out by the narrowed down topics was performed by the WP2 staff members and validated by both WP5 and the PMT in the evening of the 4th of June, so that a final list of research topics to be prioritized could be made available to the experts on the morning of the 5th of June. This process resulted in the inclusion of 15 additional topics (9 for foodborne zoonoses, 5 for antimicrobial resistance, and 1 for emerging threats) based on the re-grouping/merging of the stakeholders' needs (Appendix N) unaddressed in the narrowed down topics. The final list of research topics to be prioritized is presented here below. The topics written in blue were the narrowed down topics incorporating one or more stakeholders' needs, those in red were the additional topics based on the stakeholders' needs that were not incorporated in the narrowed down topics, and those in black were the narrowed down topics that did not incorporate any stakeholders' need.

Domain foodborne zoonoses (18 topics)

- ET3.1: Disease burden assessment of toxin producing bacteria.
- FBZ3.1: Benchmarking biosecurity practices across Europe for pigs using national level surveillance data and management practices to identify best practice to prevent HEV and *Salmonella* entering the food chain.
- FBZ4.1: Source attribution and transmission routes of foodborne pathogens other than bacteria.
- FBZ4.2: Source attribution and relative contribution routes of *T. gondii*.
- FBZ5.1: The impact of changing food consumption habits on the risk of transmission of foodborne zoonoses and AMR.
- FBZ6.1: Developing targeted and effective communication strategies to reduce risk behaviour and change attitudes of consumers concerning food borne zoonoses.
- FBZ7.1: Development of a risk assessment and management tool to prevent zoonotic bacteria, viruses and parasites in production and processing of pig meat.
- FBZ8.1: Development and validation of new in vivo models to study interactions between host, foodborne pathogens and the microbiota for investigating infection dynamics.
- FBZ9.1: Development of new tools, e.g. machine learning, to support risk assessment of STEC, *Salmonella*, *Listeria* or *Campylobacter*.
- FBZSH1: Hepatitis E virus: Development of efficient and optimised cell culture methods and virus inactivation studies in food and food production/processing environments.

- FBZSH2: Hepatitis E virus: Determining the level of contamination in foods of animal origin other than pig liver products and risk of transmission from contaminated water to food.
- FBZSH3: Source attribution studies indicating the role of the environment and non-livestock reservoirs (e.g. pets) as sources of zoonotic foodborne bacteria and antimicrobial resistance.
- FBZSH4: Global epidemiology of Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC): infections in humans and occurrence in foods and animals, as well as emergence of hybrid STEC strains.
- FBZSH5: Determinants of the reversal of the decreasing trends in incidence of *Salmonella* in humans and poultry in the EU.
- FBZSH6: Intervention studies to determine the effectiveness of preventing exposure to risk factors for *Toxoplasma gondii* infection.
- FBZSH7: Epidemiology of foodborne yersiniosis, including biotype and serotype data.
- FBZSH8: Rapid risk assessment tools for introduction of zoonotic and foodborne diseases.
- FBZSH9: Better tools for detection and investigation of foodborne outbreaks (including antimicrobial resistant pathogens), as well as economic assessments of potentially increased cluster detection through whole genome sequencing.

Antimicrobial resistance (9 topics)

- AMR2.1: Dynamics of AMR: selection, clonal spread and horizontal gene transfer in humans, animals and the environment.
- AMR4.1: Evaluating the best practice for communication and stewardship of antibiotic prescribing in humans and animals.
- AMR5.1: Risk assessment of ESBL transmission to humans from food and the environment.
- AMR6.1: Development of NGS-based tools for surveillance of AMR in Enterobacteriaceae in animals, humans and the environment.
- AMRSH1: Strengthened infection prevention and control measures, including development and assessment of interventions that prevent the development and spread of AMR.
- AMRSH2: Development of new economic models, exploring and analysing incentives to boost the development of new therapeutics, alternatives, vaccines and diagnostics for AMR.
- AMRSH3: Development of technologies that enable efficient and rapid degradation of antimicrobials in wastewater and the environment and reduce the spread of AMR.
- AMRSH4: Epidemiology of resistant microorganisms and antimicrobials into the environment and their (environment-mediated) spread.
- AMRSH5: Development of new tools for early (real-time) detection of resistant pathogens in humans and animals, as well as new diagnostic tools in particular on-site tests for humans and animals.

Emerging threats (7 topics)

- ET1.1: Development and harmonization of non-NGS methods (e.g. pheno-genotypic and histochemical methods) for the detection of food-borne parasites.
- ET2.1: Evaluation of early detection methods for emerging threats.
- ET2.2: Development of a toolkit to characterize emerging threats by combining genetic and phenotypic information.
- ET4.1: Host factors associated with increased susceptibility to infection and disease of emerging threats with undefined routes of transmission.
- ET5.1: The role of wildlife in the ecology of potentially zoonotic emerging threats.
- ET5.2: Identify key determinants of spread and persistence of foodborne zoonoses from wildlife.

- **ETSH1: Factors associated with emergence of antimicrobial resistant strains in the food supply chain.**

Research topic prioritization procedure

The prioritization procedure for the 34 research topics consisted of a multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) using an Excel tool and pre-defined criteria (defined/validated by the theme/domain secretaries and PMT in collaboration with WP2) and scoring system (defined by the PMT in collaboration with WP2) to be performed in groups and be later discussed/consolidated plenary with all experts. The procedure and supporting material for the prioritization were provided to the experts at the end of the first day (so after the narrow down session) in order to avoid biasing the narrowing down of the topics towards the prioritization criteria.

For the prioritization procedure, experts were assigned to 1 of the 3 domains indicated in the OHEJP strategy matrix (see Appendix C). Each domain was recognizable by a color:

- **Foodborne zoonoses** (secretary: Solveig Jore, FHI) → **RED**
- **Antimicrobial resistance** (secretary: Jean-Yves Madec, Anses) → **YELLOW**
- **Emerging threats** (secretary: Dan Horton, UoS) → **BLUE**

Experts were also assigned to 1 of 3 groups within each domain and asked to work together with their group members for this prioritization (Figure 3). Similar to the narrow down procedure, subdivision of experts between groups was based on their expertise over the five themes (analytical methods, host-microbe interactions, epidemiology, risk assessment, and intervention), Med/Vet orientation of their institutes, and their countries of origin (to avoid having multiple experts from the same country in the same group). This last criterion also applied to the facilitators, to avoid having facilitators of the same nationality of the experts in the group. For the groups in which a secretary was present, no "fixed" facilitators were allocated, but only "free-roaming" facilitators (see Appendix O) who moved around the different groups.

Experts were provided with the above-reported list of research topics pertaining to their respective domains. The order of topics was randomized per group to avoid any bias due to e.g. fatigue or learning-effect. To complete the MCDA, experts were asked to use their expertise and creativity, to make bold choices on occasion, and to avoid discussing the criteria themselves as these could not be changed. Each group within a domain was subsequently asked to fill in the MCDA sheet per topic in the Excel tool independently of the other groups. When all groups within a domain were finished, the scores of the MCDA per topic were summed to obtain an overall ranking within the domains. Experts were reminded that the MCDA was only meant to be a tool to support the prioritization, but that they, the experts, were free to ultimately change the ranking of the topics if they considered that this did not correctly reflect their actual domain's priorities. The overall ranking of topics was to be discussed plenary at the end of the session. The domain secretaries briefly presented the final ranking of the topics during this plenary session (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the subdivision of experts for the research topic prioritization session.

Figure 4. Schematic representation of the research topic prioritization procedure.

The MCDA had a set of attributes, or criteria, that determined the importance of a given research topic. Each criterion was composed of three (ordinal) levels with regard to the magnitude to which a topic could support the criterion itself. The aim of this prioritization was to distinguish higher-priority topics from lower-priority topics, within the set of topics that experts were provided with. Although the experts were entirely free in completing the MCDA, it was suggested to rank all the topics from high to low regarding their contribution to a given criterion. The lowest ranked topic would have then automatically fallen into the lowest criterion level, and the highest ranked topic into the highest level. Experts could then subsequently divide the other topics among these criteria-levels according to their contribution relative to these topics. After completing this ranking for each criterion, the Excel tool could have been filled accordingly.

For the MCDA of research topics, 7 criteria were defined, these were:

- C1: Inclusion of the human, animal and environmental components
- C2: Potential direct impact to decrease disease and/or economic burden for humans and animals
- C3: Potential indirect impact to decrease the disease and economic burden for humans and animals
- C4: Number of stakeholders from whom the research needs are addressed
- C5: Foreseen strengthening of alignment between partners
- C6: Strategic interactions with other ongoing or completed EU projects and/or initiatives
- C7: The level of innovation that a research topic enables

Each criterion was explained to the experts and handouts were distributed so that the experts could always consult the definitions of the criteria and their scores. Descriptions and scoring levels of these criteria are reported in Appendix T. Criterion 4 (C4) and criterion 6 (C6) could be completed by consulting handouts distributed to the experts and appended to this report (Appendix L and Appendix N, respectively).

In MCDA, it might be the case that some criteria are more important than others. This difference in relative importance is represented by weighing criteria when computing the final ranking score (this generates a weighted average). Whether or not some of the OHEJP criteria were more important than others was determined by the PMT. To this end, a formal and structured weights assessment was conducted among the PMT members using the swing-weighting method. The final weights that were used for the ranking of research topics are shown in Appendix Z.

Integrative topic prioritization procedure

For the prioritization of the integrative topics, 6 groups of 6-7 experts each plus 1 facilitator were made at random with a “lottery” system. In each of these groups, an expert acted as secretary. Experts were asked to prioritize the 5 integrative topics listed here below using, once again, a MCDA procedure. This list of integrative topics was provided to the experts in a randomized order, along with their full descriptions (see Appendix P).

IA-1: Common frameworks for design and methods to assess equivalence between surveillance and control activities.

IA-2: Harmonized protocols and common best practice.

IA-3: Joint databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata.

IA-6: Mentoring (twinning) system for sharing of best intervention practice.

IA-7: Aligned use of experimental facilities and models (of transmission, ecology, risk assessment etc.).

These topics were the 5 integrative topics that were not selected in the first round of project proposals. The integrative topics no. 4 (interpretation of surveillance data - Standardized data formats and ontologies, common tools and procedures for data analyses, including interpretation of sequence data) and no. 5 (common reporting and signalling procedures, joint platform for sharing surveillance data and their interpretation, incl. risk assessments) were not included in the prioritization since the gap analysis revealed that they were sufficiently covered by the first round projects (see Appendix F).

Each group was asked to complete the MCDA in the Excel file per integrative topic independently of the other groups. When all groups were finished, the scores of the MCDA per topic were summed to obtain the overall prioritization. Experts were reminded that the MCDA was only meant to be a tool to support prioritization, but that they, the experts, could ultimately change the ranking of the topics if they thought that this did not correctly reflect the consensus priorities. Instructions and suggestions given to the experts to complete the MCDA for integrative topics were similar to those given for the research topics. However, the integrative activities are different than the research ones as they aim to address significant bottlenecks or omissions in the joint response capacity to One Health challenges or increase the capacity to compensate for any suboptimal response. The response capacity intended here covered all areas along the chain of prevention, detection and mitigation. For example, if there is no joint understanding and clarity in the way risks are assessed and communicated, then this may impact a timely and effective response, or if laboratory capacity is insufficient in areas where a certain One Health issue first presents itself, then this might delay an effective recognition and response to the issue. The MCDA exercise for the integrative topics was therefore constructed as decision support tool to prioritize the identified integrative activities in their ability to strengthen this joint response capacity by tackling the most important issues.

For the MCDA of integrative topics, 6 criteria were defined, these were:

- ITC1: Number of needs expressed by One Health EJP partners that are addressed
- ITC2: Number of needs expressed by stakeholders that are addressed
- ITC3: Recurrence of the issue addressed by the integrative topic across domains
- ITC4: Integration along the axis of the 'prevention, detection and response'-chain
- ITC5: Effects of the integrative topic on the joint response capacity
- ITC6: Strategic interactions with other ongoing or completed EU projects and/or initiatives

Each criterion of this MCDA was explained to the experts and handouts were distributed so that the experts could always consult the definitions of the criteria and their scores. Descriptions and scoring levels of these criteria are reported in Appendix U. The criteria for the MCDA for the integrative topics could be completed by consulting handouts distributed to the experts and appended to this report (see Appendix Q to S). Similar to the MCDA for research topics, the relative importance among these criteria was assessed by the PMT. The procedure for the weights assessment was the same as for the research topics, but with different criteria. See Appendix Z for the final weights.

Outcome of the research topic prioritization

The prioritization procedure resulted in 3 provisional lists of prioritized research topics for foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance, and emerging threats, respectively. During the plenary discussions, experts provided suggestions on how to reword some topic titles in order to make them clearer and/or to stress some specific aspects that are the focus of these topics. Moreover, experts suggested merging topic FBZ4.2 with topic FBZ4.1, and topic AMRSH4 with topic AMR2.1. By incorporating these suggestions, the provisional lists of prioritized

research topics are as follows:

Foodborne zoonoses (17 topics)

1. FBZSH3: Source attribution of bacterial foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance considering also the environment and non-livestock reservoirs (e.g. pets and wildlife) as sources (Ranking score: 0.76).
2. FBZ3.1: Benchmarking biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe using national surveillance data and management standards for identifying best practice to prevent biological hazards, particularly *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus, from entering the food supply chain (Ranking score: 0.75).
3. FBZ4.1: Source attribution and transmission routes of foodborne pathogens other than bacteria, with emphasis on *Toxoplasma gondii* (Ranking score: 0.72, considering the highest of the two merged topics).
4. FBZSH5: Determinants of the reversal of the decreasing trend in *Salmonella* incidence in humans and poultry in the EU (Ranking score: 0.70).
5. FBZSH9: Better tools for detection and investigation of foodborne outbreaks, including antimicrobial resistant pathogens, as well as economic assessments of potentially increased cluster detection through whole genome sequencing (Ranking score: 0.67).
6. FBZSH8: Rapid risk assessment tools for introduction of zoonotic and foodborne diseases (Ranking score: 0.65).
7. FBZSH6: Intervention studies to determine the effectiveness of preventing exposure to risk factors for *Toxoplasma gondii* infection (Ranking score: 0.65).
8. FBZ7.1: Development of a risk assessment and management tool to prevent zoonotic bacteria, viruses and parasites in production and processing of pig meat (Ranking score: 0.63).
9. FBZSH7: Epidemiology of foodborne yersiniosis, including biotype and serotype data (Ranking score: 0.59).
10. FBZSH4: Global epidemiology of Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC): infections in humans and occurrence in foods and animals, as well as emergence of hybrid STEC strains (Ranking score: 0.59).
11. FBZSH1: Hepatitis E virus: Development of efficient and optimized cell culture methods and virus inactivation studies in food and food production/processing environments (Ranking score: 0.55).
12. FBZ9.1: Development of new tools, e.g. machine learning, to support risk assessment of STEC, (*Salmonella*, *Listeria* or *Campylobacter*) (Ranking score: 0.53).
13. FBZSH2: Hepatitis E virus: Determining the level of contamination in foods of animal origin other than pig liver products and risk of transmission from contaminated water to food (Ranking score: 0.53).
14. FBZ5.1: The impact of changing food consumption habits on the risk of transmission of foodborne zoonoses and AMR (Ranking score: 0.50).
15. FBZ6.1: Developing targeted and effective communication strategies to reduce risk behavior and change attitudes of consumers concerning food borne zoonoses (Ranking score: 0.45).
16. ET3.1: Disease burden assessment of toxin producing bacteria (Ranking score: 0.43).
17. FBZ8.1: Development and validation of new *in vivo* models to study interactions between host, foodborne pathogens and the microbiota for investigating infection dynamics (Ranking score: 0.43).

Antimicrobial resistance (8 topics)

1. AMRSH5: Development of new tools for early (real-time) detection of resistant pathogens in humans and animals, as well as new diagnostic tools, in particular on-site tests for humans and animals (Ranking score: 0.66).
2. AMR2.1: Dynamics of AMR selection, clonal spread and horizontal gene transfer in humans, animals and the environment, including epidemiology of resistant microorganisms and antimicrobials in the environment

and their (environment-mediated) spread (Ranking score: 0.62, considering the highest of the two merged topics).

3. AMR6.1: Development of NGS-based tools for surveillance of AMR in Enterobacteriaceae in animals, humans and the environment (Ranking score: 0.60).
4. AMRSH1: Strengthened infection prevention and control measures, including development and assessment of interventions that prevent the development and spread of AMR (Ranking score: 0.57).
5. AMR4.1: Evaluating the best practice for communication and stewardship of antibiotic prescribing in humans and animals (Ranking score: 0.57).
6. AMRSH3: Development of technologies that enable efficient and rapid degradation of antimicrobials in wastewater and the environment and reduce the spread of AMR (Ranking score: 0.52).
7. AMRSH2: Development of new economic models, exploring and analyzing incentives to boost the development of new therapeutics, alternatives, vaccines and diagnostics for AMR (Ranking score: 0.46).
8. AMR5.1: Risk assessment of ESBL transmission to humans from food and the environment (Ranking score: 0.43).

Emerging threats (7 topics)

1. ET2.2: Development of a toolkit to characterize emerging threats by combining genomic and phenotypic information (Ranking score: 0.78).
2. ET1.1: Development and harmonization of NGS and non-NGS methods (e.g. pheno-genotypic and histochemical methods) for the detection of foodborne parasites (Ranking score: 0.66).
3. ET5.2: Identification of key determinants of spread and persistence of foodborne zoonoses from wildlife
4. ET2.1: Evaluation of early detection methods for emerging threats (Ranking score: 0.62).
5. ETSH1: Factors associated with emergence of antimicrobial resistant strains in the food supply chain (Ranking score: 0.58).
6. ET5.1: The role of wildlife in the ecology of potentially zoonotic emerging threats (Ranking score: 0.54).
7. ET4.1: Host factors associated with increased susceptibility to infection and disease of emerging threats with undefined routes of transmission (Ranking score: 0.46).

Outcome of the integrative topic prioritization

The prioritization procedure of integrative topics resulted in a provisional list of prioritized integrative topics, which is reported here below. However, two of the six groups of experts did not have enough time to find a consensus for filling in criterion ITC1 (i.e. number of partners' needs addressed), and the other 4 groups reported high uncertainty in their answers to this criterion. It was therefore decided by the PMT members present on site that this criterion, being objectively addressable by counting the partners needs reported in Appendix R, would be filled in by WP2/WP4 staff after the meeting and used for all groups. Criterion ITC6 (strategic Interactions) was not assessed for IA-6 and IA-7 by 1 group, and the average of the other groups was therefore imputed to be able to compute a final ranking score. The provisional list of prioritized integrative topics is as follows:

1. IA-3: Joint databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata (Ranking score: 0.73)
2. IA-2: Harmonized protocols and common best practice (Ranking score: 0.72)

3. IA-1: Common frameworks for design and methods to assess equivalence between surveillance and control activities (Ranking score: 0.72)
4. IA-6: Mentoring (twinning) system for sharing of best intervention practice (Ranking score: 0.49)
5. IA-7: Aligned use of experimental facilities and models (of transmission, ecology, risk assessment etc.) (Ranking score: 0.43)

Next steps

The provisional lists of priority research topics identified and ranked by the experts, including how the suggestions made by the experts have been taken into account, as well as the preliminary list of priority integrative topics including comments on how gaps in scoring have been taken into account, were sent to the PMT for approval. Once approved, these lists were included in the present report. This report was then validated by the secretaries and the PMT, and distributed to all participants of the experts meeting. Also, the provisional lists of priority research and integrative topics were sent to the members of the Stakeholders' Committee (SC) and discussed at the SC meeting on June 21st, during which additional input on what the prioritized topics should address was collected. After the SC meeting, the PMT may decide to modify the lists of priority topics based on the outcome of such consultation. Moreover, the PMT will shorten the lists of priority research topics proportional to the budget allocated to the research domains and integrative activities. For those research topics in the updated lists, topics descriptions will be developed by WP2 in collaboration with the domain and theme secretaries, to be validated by the PMT. These lists and descriptions will be provided as input for the Scientific Steering Board (SSB) meeting on the 2nd of October 2018.

Group photo of the OHEJP experts meeting, 4-5 June 2018, RIVM, Bilthoven, the Netherlands

APPENDIX A: Programme of the Experts Meeting

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Date	4-5 June 2018
Venue	RIVM, Bilthoven, the Netherlands
Meeting	Experts Meeting
Room	T0.07

Meeting agenda

11:00-17:30

EXPERTS MEETING Day 1: 4 June 2018

- 11:00-11:30 **Arrival & Coffee**
- 11:30-11:35 **Welcome, Jaap van Dissel (RIVM)**
- 11:35-11:45 **Objectives of the experts meeting, Arjen van de Giessen (RIVM)**
- 11:45-12:05 **Procedure for narrowing down the research topics, Lapo Mughini-Gras (RIVM)**
- 12:05-12:15 **European stakeholders' needs, Annemarie Kaesbohrer (BfR)**
- 12:15-12:25 **Strategic interactions with other EU projects and initiatives, Lucía de Juan Ferré (UCM)**
- 12:25-12:35 **Gap analysis of first round topics, Lapo Mughini-Gras (RIVM)**
- 12:35-12:45 **Questions**
- 12:45-13:45 **Lunch**
- 13:45-15:45 **Topics narrow down session**
- 15:45-16:15 **Coffee break**
- 16:15-17:15 **Presentation of narrowed down topics (plenary session)**
- 17:15-17:30 **Transportation to the Van der Valk Hotel in De Bilt**
- 19:00 **Dinner at the restaurant De Witte Zwaan in De Bilt**

08:30-16:00

EXPERTS MEETING Day 2: 5 June 2018

- 08:30-09:00 **Arrival**
- 09:00-09:30 **Summary of the narrowed down topics & prioritization procedure, Martijn Bouwknecht (RIVM)**
- 09:30-11:45 **Research topics prioritization session**
- 11:00-11:15 **Coffee break**
- 11:45-12:30 **Within-domain group discussion of prioritized research topics**
- 12:30-13:30 **Lunch**
- 13:30-14:00 **Presentation of prioritized research topics (plenary session)**
- 14:00-15:30 **Integrative topics prioritization session**
- 15:30-16:00 **Presentation of prioritized integrative topics (plenary session)**
- 16:00 **End of the experts meeting**

Decisions to be adopted during the experts meeting

Decision	Support documents	Management Body	Vote Requirements
To narrow down the research topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• National priorities• Gaps in current work plan• European stakeholders' needs• Other EU projects/initiatives• Guidelines/checklist• List of topics	WP2	N/A
To prioritize the research and integrative topics for the second round of project proposals	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• MCDA tool• Description of (narrowed down) research topics• Description of integrative topics• European stakeholders' needs• Other EU projects/initiatives• Guidelines/checklist	WP2	N/A

APPENDIX B: Attendance list of the experts meeting

Organisation	Participants	Role
01 – ANSES	Jean-Yves Madec	Expert, domain secretary AMR
02 – ANSES	Andre Jestin	PMT member
03 – AGES	Sabine Schlager	Expert
04 – CODA-CERVA	Hein Imberechts	PMT member, facilitator
05 – WIV-ISP- IPH	Steven van Gucht	Expert
06 - NDRVMI	Gergana Krumova-Valcheva	Expert
07 – NIPH	Barbora Mackova	Expert
08 – VRI	Renata Karpiskova	Expert
09 – BFR	Karsten Nöckler	Expert, substitute theme secretary HMI
10 – FLI	Herbert Tomaso	Expert
11 – RKI	Mirko Faber	Expert
12 – DTU	Maarten Nauta**	Expert & theme secretary RA
13 – SSI	Henrik Vedel Nielsen	Expert
14 – VFL	Triin Tedersoo	Expert
15 – INIA	Miguel Angel Jimenez	Expert
16 – UCM	Bruno Gonzalez Zorn*	Expert, theme secretary HMI
17 – UCM	Lucia de Juan	PMT member, facilitator
18 – INRA	Philippe Velge	Expert
19 – IPP	Philippe Glaser	Expert
20 – APHA	Chris Teale	Expert
21 – PHE	Amanda Walsh	Expert
22 – NUIG	Louise O'Connor	Expert
23 – NUIG	Kis Zoltan	Expert
24 – TEAGASC	Kieran Jordan	Expert
25 – ISS	Stefano Morabito	Expert, theme secretary AM
26 – IZSAM	Francesco Pomilio	Expert
27 – IZLSER	Giovanni Alborali	Expert
28 – RIVM	Arjen van de Giessen	PMT member, WP2 staff, facilitator
29 – RIVM	Joke van der Giessen	Expert
30 – RIVM	Lapo Mughini Gras	WP2 staff, Facilitator
31 – WBVR	Dik Mevius	Expert
32 – FHI	Solveig Jore	Expert, domain secretary FBZ
33 – NVI	Merete Hofshagen	Expert, theme secretary INT

Organisation	Participants	Role
34 – PIWET	Dariusz Wasyl	Expert, theme secretary EPI
35 – INIAV	Ana Botelho	Expert
36 – INSA	Rita Sousa	Expert
37 – IISPV	Laurentiu Ciupescu	Expert
38 – SLV	Jakob Ottoson	Expert
39 – FoHM	Sara Byfors	Expert
40 – SVA	Stefan Börjesson	Expert
41 – SVA	Ann Lindberg	PMT member, facilitator
42 – UTARTU	Veljo Kisand	Expert
42 - University Surrey	Dan Horton	Expert, domain secretary ET
43- University Surrey	Roberto La Ragione	PMT member, facilitator
44 - ISS	Luca Busani	PMT member, facilitator
45 - BfR	Annemarie Käsbohrer	PMT member, facilitator
46 - RIVM	Martijn Bouwknecht	WP2 staff, facilitator

*Absent on both days of the meeting. **Absent on the second day of the meeting.

APPENDIX D: Subdivision of the experts between subgroups within themes

THEME	SUBGROUP	Uni_GROUP	Expert	Institute	Country	Domain expertise	Vet/Med	Facilitator	COLOR
Analytical methods	1	AM-1	Ana Botelho	INIAV	PT	FBZ	Vet	Free role	Red
Analytical methods	1	AM-1	Dik Mevius	WBVR	NL	AMR	Vet		Red
Analytical methods	1	AM-1	Stefano Morabito	ISS	IT	ET	Med		Red
Analytical methods	1	AM-1	Sabine Schlager	AGES	AT	FBZ	Med		Red
Analytical methods	2	AM-2	Jean-Yves Madec	ANSES	FR	AMR	Vet	Hein	Red
Analytical methods	2	AM-2	Kis Zoltan	NCE	HU	ET	Vet		Red
Analytical methods	2	AM-2	Sara Byfors	FoHM	SE	AMR	Med		Red
Analytical methods	2	AM-2	Henrik Vedel Nielsen	SSI	DK	FBZ	Med		Red
Host-microbe interaction	1	HMI-1	Karsten Nöckler	BfR	DE	FBZ	Vet	Free role	Green
Host-microbe interaction	1	HMI-1	Gergana Krumova-Valcheva	NDRVMI	BG	FBZ	Vet		Green
Host-microbe interaction	1	HMI-1	Bruno González-Zorn	VISA VET-UCM	ES	AMR	Vet		Green
Host-microbe interaction	1	HMI-1	Philippe Velge	INRA	FR	ET	Vet		Green
Host-microbe interaction	1	HMI-1	Louise O'Connor	NIJG	IE	AMR	Med		Green
Host-microbe interaction	2	HMI-2	Laurentiu Mihai Ciupescu	IISPV	RO	FBZ	Vet	Annemarie	Green
Host-microbe interaction	2	HMI-2	Triin Tedersoo	VFL	EE	AMR	Vet		Green
Host-microbe interaction	2	HMI-2	Miguel Angel Jimenez	INIA	ES	ET	Vet		Green
Host-microbe interaction	2	HMI-2	Steven Van Gucht	Sciensano	BE	ET	Med		Green
Epidemiology	1	EPI-1	Dariusz Wasyl	Piwet	PL	FBZ	Vet	Free role	Blue
Epidemiology	1	EPI-1	Stefan Börjesson	SVA	SE	AMR	Vet		Blue
Epidemiology	1	EPI-1	Rita Sousa	INSA	PT	ET	Med		Blue
Epidemiology	1	EPI-1	Philippe Glaser	IP	FR	AMR	Med		Blue
Epidemiology	1	EPI-1	Mirko Faber	RKI	DE	FBZ	Med		Blue
Epidemiology	2	EPI-2	Herbert Tomaso	FLI	DE	ET	Vet	Lucia	Blue
Epidemiology	2	EPI-2	Chris Teale	APHA	UK	AMR	Vet		Blue
Epidemiology	2	EPI-2	Joke van der Giesen	RIVM	NL	ET	Med		Blue
Epidemiology	2	EPI-2	Solveig Jore	FHI	NO	FBZ	Med		Blue
Risk assessment	1	RA-1	Renata Karpšková	VRI	CZ	FBZ	Vet	Free role	Yellow
Risk assessment	1	RA-1	Maarten Nauta	DTU	DK	FBZ	Vet		Yellow
Risk assessment	1	RA-1	Jakob Ottoson	SLV	SE	AMR	Vet		Yellow
Risk assessment	1	RA-1	Veljo Kisand	UTARTU	EE	AMR	Med		Yellow
Risk assessment	1	RA-1	Barbora Macková	NIPH	CZ	ET	Med		Yellow
Intervention	1	INT-1	Merete Hofshagen	NVI	NO	FBZ	Vet	Free role	Orange
Intervention	1	INT-1	Giovanni Alborali	IZSLER	IT	AMR	Vet		Orange
Intervention	1	INT-1	Amanda Walsh	PHE	UK	ET	Med		Orange
Intervention	2	INT-2	Francesco Pomilio	IZSAM	IT	FBZ	Vet		Orange
Intervention	2	INT-2	Kieran Jordan	TEAGASC	IE	AMR	Vet		Orange
Intervention	2	INT-2	Dan Horton	Surrey	UK	ET	Vet	Orange	

APPENDIX E: List of research topics to be narrowed down

Overview of the research topics

Topic code	Topic title	Theme of reference	Selected in first round	Included in narrow down
Foodborne Zoonoses (FBZ)				
FBZ-1	Improved surveillance system and harmonized data analyses	Epidemiology	Yes	No
FBZ-2	Development and harmonisation of NGS-based methods for detection and tracing of FBZ agents, emerging threats and AMR determinants	Analytical methods	Yes	No
FBZ-3	Biosecurity and other interventions	Intervention	Yes	Yes
FBZ-4	Source attribution and transmission routes	Epidemiology	Yes	Yes
FBZ-5	Epidemiological studies: risk factors and dynamics	Epidemiology	No	Yes
FBZ-6	Risk communication and consumer targeted intervention strategies	Intervention	No	Yes
FBZ-7	Optimizing options for risk management and enforcement in feed and food production and processing	Intervention	No	Yes
FBZ-8	Model Systems (in vitro and in vivo) to study host/food – microbe interactions	Host-microbe interaction	No	Yes
FBZ-9	Frameworks and systems for sharing tools and data for risk assessment and effective decision making	Risk assessment	No	Yes
Antimicrobial resistance (AMR)				
AMR-1	Development and harmonisation of phenotypic methods	Analytical methods	Yes	No
AMR-2	Epidemiological studies into the dynamics of AMR in human and animal populations and the environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR	Epidemiology	Yes	Yes
AMR-3	Risk assessment of AMR	Risk assessment	Yes	No
AMR-4	Communication and stewardship of AMR	Intervention	No	Yes
AMR-5	Disease burden, socio-economic consequences and risk ranking	Risk assessment	No	Yes
AMR-6	Metagenomics and bioinformatics for detection and surveillance of AMR pathogens and determinants	Analytical methods	No	Yes
Emerging threats (ET)				
ET-1	Development and harmonisation of non-NGS-based methods for detection of FBZ agents and emerging threats	Analytical methods	Yes	Yes
ET-2	Improving preparedness and response	Epidemiology	No	Yes
ET-3	Applying risk assessment/modelling methodologies to support decisions for the control of emerging threats, foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance	Risk assessment	No	Yes
ET-4	Host factors associated with colonization, persistence and disease	Host-microbe interaction	No	Yes
ET-5	Ecology of emerging pathogens	Epidemiology	No	Yes

Overview of the research topics to be narrowed down placed within the OH-EJP Matrix

THEMES	DOMAINES		
	Foodborne zoonoses (FBZ) <i>Solverig Jore</i>	Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) <i>Jean-Yves Madec</i>	Emerging threats (ET) <i>Dan Horton</i>
Analytical methods <i>Stefano Morabito</i>		AMR-6	ET-1
Host-microbe interaction <i>Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn</i>	FBZ-8		ET-4
Epidemiology <i>Dariusz Wasyl</i>	FBZ-4 FBZ-5	AMR-2	ET-2 ET-5
Risk assessment <i>Marteen Nauta</i>	FBZ-9	AMR-5	ET-3
Intervention <i>Marete Hofshagen</i>	FBZ-3 FBZ-6 FBZ-7	AMR-4	

Theme ANALYTICAL METHODS

Topic AMR-6: Metagenomics and bioinformatics for detection and surveillance of AMR pathogens and determinants

Context

The development of the NGS technology has given access to a deep characterization of genomes of isolated AMR bacteria and allowed new insights in deciphering the spread of AMR determinants among pathogens and/or commensals in humans and animals. On the other hand, culture-independent strategies referred to as metagenomics provide new and global approaches to investigate the distribution and features of AMR determinants from complex microbiota and are promising (ECDC: [Expert Opinion](#) on the introduction of next-generation typing methods for food- and waterborne diseases in the EU and EEA, 2015).

Objectives

The overall objective is to enforce WGS metagenomics approaches in the monitoring of AMR development in complex microbiota recovered from relevant sites under selective pressure with antibiotics. This would include specific expected hotspots of AMR selection such as at hospital or farm level, or in the environment. The objectives should be tuned with FBZ-2, 'NGS-based methods'.

Expected results

- Production of quantitative WGS metagenomic data in geographical sites of human or veterinary (or combined) relevance
- Correlation of metagenomic data with antibiotic usages and other risk factors
- Tools for quantification of AMR determinants in metagenomic data
- Link to integrative topic 2: develop harmonized protocols for metagenomic analysis in various matrices.

Topic ET-1: Development and harmonisation of non-NGS-based methods for detection of FBZ agents and emerging threats

Context

Public health and veterinary systems are constantly burdened by potential epidemics caused by new and emerging zoonoses, either food-borne or not. The methods used to detect zoonotic agents are often long and cumbersome and do not cover the entire spectrum of threats. The lack of rapid and comprehensive analytical approaches negatively affect management of human infections, trade, food chain sustainability and food security. Technology increasingly allows developing or re-directing analytical methodologies for the detection of pathogens, which are more rapid and reliable than the standard approaches based on cultural strategies and potentially can cover pathogens that are currently not identifiable or misdiagnosed. Such technologies have the potential to deliver rapid assays on platforms applicable to field use such as bed/farm/pen-side tests, as well as in the food production chain.

Objectives

The overall objectives will be to fill the gaps in the knowledge of the methodologies alternative to standard PCR or cultural isolation applicable to food-borne zoonoses and emerging threats. The research will focus on zoonotic agents of EU priority as supported by EU level prioritisation exercises, strategic research agendas or similar. The setup of methods not based on NGS and harmonized scheme for their use will be the main focus of the call, with emphasis on the development innovative sampling or sample preparation techniques.

Specific aims:

- The development of approaches for the pheno/genotypic (non-NGS-based) detection of new zoonotic agents and emerging threats covering all the process from sampling to sample preparation and analysis of results (research objective)
- The development of rapid and reliable non-NGS-based tools for the detection of new zoonotic agents and emerging threats at bed/pen/farm-site or other locations in the food production chain (research objective)
- The optimisation and validation of existing and newly developed methods for the pheno/genotypic (non-NGS-based) detection of new zoonotic agents and emerging threats (research objective- in collaboration with integrative topic 3)

Expected results

- Harmonized procedures for pheno/genotypic detection of new zoonotic agents and emerging threats (Deliverable).
- Validated, rapid and reliable non-NGS-based methods for pheno/genotypic detection of new zoonotic agents and emerging threats (Deliverable).
- Proficiency Testing schemes for the assessment of the performance parameters of the optimised/developed methods for the pheno-genotypic (non-NGS) detection of new zoonotic agents and emerging threats (Impact on the collaboration between EJP partners- in collaboration with integrative topic 3)

Theme HOST-MICROBE INTERACTION

Topic FBZ-8: Model Systems (in vitro and in vivo) to study host/food – microbe interactions

Context

- Model systems are crucial to understand the pathogenesis, emergence and spread of infectious diseases.
- The use of animal and cellular systems elicits the understanding of the outcome of a given disease and results in novel approaches to fight against diseases.
- The use of models involving interaction of microbes with food or spread in the food chain, remain an important tool to ensure consumer safety.
- Mathematical models increase our ability to understand, and ultimately predict, the behaviour of pathogens in their hosts as well as the spread of the contamination throughout the food chain and the geographic distribution of spread of disease.
- The genetic content of microbes is dynamic, and gives rise to new emerging pathogens, representing a threat to consumers and animal populations.
- The identification of virulence factors can lead to the construction of avirulent mutants and their use as new vaccines, like the novel European TB vaccine (e.g. <http://www.tbvi.eu/>).
- The development of alternatives to animal models is a priority in the EU and world-wide_ <http://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC97811/lbna27474enn.pdf>

Objectives

- To develop novel in vivo models (both animal models and alternatives such as cellular systems) that reflect infection in the natural host, that opens the door to understand the pathogenesis of infectious diseases. To use these models to study the pathogenesis of microbial diseases.
- To develop models to study interaction, survival and spread of microbes in food or the food production chain.
- To develop new mathematical approaches to dissect the behaviour of microbes within a host or their geographical dissemination
- Identification of viral/bacteria/parasitic markers that characterize microbial threats for animal and/or human populations
- Identify and tackle potential pathogens in the environment.
- To characterize the interaction of microbes with their host.

Expected results

- New animal/cellular models to study infectious diseases.
- Mathematical models that describe and predict emergence and spread of food-borne pathogens from host, to food and in the food chain.
- Increase animal welfare by optimizing animal models or developing alternative approaches.
- Recognition of Virulence/Resistance markers that play an important role in fast identification of microbial threats in the food chain.
- Identification of new virulence factors or new combinations of existing factors that can lead to new drug targets against microbial pathogens.

Topic ET-4: Host factors associated with colonization, persistence and disease

Context

The elements defining host specificity of microbes is poorly understood. Crossing of the

species barriers represents a crucial event in emergence of known and novel diseases. Understanding the host factors that determine the flow between carriage, persistence and disease represents a major challenge to develop effective control measures of given pathogens. Recent evidence suggests that the microbiota may be involved in host specificity.

The project proposal should clearly indicate that the work has not been done in the context of other EU projects.

Objectives

- To help elucidate our knowledge on the host factors that determine host specificity.
- To better understand humoral/cellular immune response and its implementation to control microbial infections and its role in latency/sub-clinical infections.
- To increase our understanding of the relevance of the microbiome and the host specificity of microbes.
- To study pathogen virulence factors that are associated with colonization, persistence, latency and disease
- To unify efforts within the EU to tackle spread of microbes to new hosts.

Expected results

- Increased knowledge on host factors associated with colonization, persistence and disease
- Link to integrative topic 3: Multi-microbial experts will share knowledge to create a multi- microbial hub to share knowledge and techniques to study host specificity.

Theme EPIDEMIOLOGY

Topic FBZ-4: Source attribution and transmission routes

Context

EU foodborne zoonoses surveillance systems and antimicrobial resistance monitoring target specific threat/source combination. Having assumed zoonotic origin of relevant public health threats, systematic studies on source attribution and transmission routes have been focused on a few aspects. Improved evidence-based knowledge including zoonotic and/or anthrozoönotic transmission and human-to-human spread is needed.

Objectives

The study should:

- focus on food- and water-borne pathogens, either bacteria, viruses, fungi, parasites, as well as antimicrobial resistance and its transmissible elements, prioritized by EU level prioritisation exercises, strategic research agendas or similar
- aim at identification of reservoirs, sources, vehicles, and routes of pathogen transmission applying a One Health approach
- impose ecological approach, not limited to farm-to-fork concept, food of animal origin, or animal to human transmission. Instead, the role of environment, wildlife and non-food producing animals, globalisation (imports, travels, etc.), and/or human behaviour is anticipated,
- address human impact on ecology of pathogens and antimicrobial resistance,
- involve both conventional and novel (NGS-based) techniques,
- develop or improve pipelines or models for source attribution,
- to critically assess and improve existing models for source attribution

- facilitate an integrated approach between source and outcome by data sharing. (link to integrative topic 5)

Expected results

The project will

- improve knowledge on sources and transmission routes of pathogens and AMR determinants within ecosystems, including food chain,
- provide sound methods and baseline information to guide risk assessment and management, including platforms for sharing new approaches to attribute cases of FBZ and AMR to their sources (link to integrative topic 5)

Topic FBZ-5: Epidemiological studies: risk factors and dynamics

Context

EU foodborne zoonoses surveillance systems target specific threat/source combinations, whereas emerging threats require identification of agent and possible route of infection. In both scenarios identification of risk factors and infection dynamics might serve to improve the effectiveness of surveillance systems and optimize the use of time and resources.

Objectives

The study should focus on infectious agents included in current zoonoses and emerging threats surveillance. The project should:

- collect epidemiological metadata and metagenomic data from representative clinical cases to identify threats relevant for human or animal populations,
- determine the impact of dissemination of hazards due to movements of humans and animals, trade of goods (including feed and food), geographical and seasonal distribution, climate and demographic changes, alimentation patterns and habits on the dynamics and risks posed by foodborne and emerging threats,
- verify or identify risk factors and optimal control points for foodborne and emerging threats,
- develop models to predict pathogen transmission and dynamics related to the identified risk factors.

Expected results

The study should facilitate joint action of partner organizations. The project will

- identify risk factors for a range of foodborne and emerging threats for future prioritisation, ranking and intervention,
- assess dynamics of foodborne and emerging threats,
- demonstrate the added value through linkage with the European monitoring and surveillance managed by EFSA and ECDC
- identify optimal control points to reduce public health consequences of foodborne and emerging threats.

Topic AMR-2: Epidemiological studies into the dynamics of AMR in human and animals populations and the environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR

Context

Although multiple efforts have been undertaken there are still knowledge gaps and inconsistencies in understanding of the epidemiology of antimicrobial resistance, i.e. its

selection and spread under antimicrobial usage pressure in different ecological settings. Geographical differences, temporal trends, variable farming, environmental reservoirs, wildlife, farm and companion animals as well as human colonization, anthropogenic impact on the abundance of resistance in the environment, and factors promoting or mitigating resistance transmission need systematic studies.

Objectives

The study should add to, but not replicate, current knowledge. Multidisciplinary approach including microbiology, genomics (i.e. WGS), epidemiology should address several of the below areas:

- Investigate geographical differences and trends in antimicrobial usage and resistance in the environment, human (including exposure groups) and animal populations, based on current, available monitoring programmes in the EU.
- Study the influence of animal management (including antimicrobial usage) on the occurrence and spread of resistance,
- Clarify associations between consequences of antimicrobial usage and levels and spread of resistance; develop appropriate methodologies.
- Study associations between antimicrobial usage and resistance in bacteria from food animals, companion animals and humans
- Study associations between resistance mechanisms in bacteria of environmental, animal and human origin,
- Special attention should be paid to multidrug and emerging resistances, as well as resistance to critically important antimicrobials for human and animal treatment,
- Study the origin and transmission dynamics of resistant bacteria (i.e. import versus local selection, zoonotic versus anthropogenic versus environmental)
- Study clonal spread of resistant bacteria versus horizontal gene transfer in the dissemination of resistance within One Health approach. These might include fitness cost studies.

Expected results

The results are expected to provide evidence on the epidemiology of resistance, namely:

- a better description of reservoirs and vectors of resistance,
- increased knowledge on environmental, geographical and demographic risk factors, drivers and catalysers of selection and trends in resistance,
- more awareness of the ecological consequences of antimicrobial usage,
- increased knowledge on the dynamics and transmission routes of AMR for future prioritisation and interventions.
- Models, instructions or guidelines are developed that enable to study the link between antimicrobial usage and resistance.

Topic ET-2: Improving preparedness and response

Context

Natural disasters and microbiological threats are often unpredictable, nevertheless we want to try to reduce the effects they can cause by trying to detect and identify them and as much as possible eliminate or prevent them. In spite of implementation across Europe of networks (EWRS, EMERGE, ENIV, RASFF) for signaling of microbiological threats, including imported emerging pathogens, food- transmitted or zoonotic, and exchange information, there is still potential for improvement of preparedness and response to such threats. It should be pointed out that new microbiological threats may be a result of

changes in human behavior, as well as implementation of new processing or preservation methods (food, water) but also differences in national regulations. There is a need to develop methods and tools suitable to early detection, identification and control of emerging threats but specially to fast and appropriate decision making and effective response.

Objectives

The main aim is to build integrated capacity for European public health and veterinary laboratories to detect, control and prevent emerging diseases in the Europe. The activities to be undertaken within the scope of this part of the EJP, focused on improving preparedness and response to emerging threats, might encompass the following actions:

- Development of methods and tools to early identify, detect and control emerging threats, – including novel tools for data collection, analyses and data sharing - in cooperation with established networks like EMERGE, ENIVD, EWRS, IHR; focused on microbial, zoonotic, food- borne bacterial, viral and parasitic threats as well as on their emerging AM mechanisms or virulence patterns. The main goal will be to develop tools that will be effective in spite of the well-known phenomenon of high variability and variety of microbial threats as well as different carriers or way of transmission.
- Development of modern methods/tools for decision making and intervention: evaluation of already established methods/tools including their compatibility to national regulations and systems across Europe as well as Europe networks; optimization and validation of developed methods/tools; training.

Expected results

Building of an integrated European - broad surveillance - response program, based on a MedVet EJP network, to detect, control and prevent emerging diseases appearing in Europe or potentially introduced in Europe will be the main goal of the project. The main goal of this part of project: improvement preparedness and response to emerging threats is expected by:

- developed modern and integrated tools / algorithms for early detection and control of emerging threats (animal-, feed-, food-, water- or environment transmitted), as well as for crisis communication, decision making and response across Europe (link to integrative topics 4 and 5);
- Evaluation of effectiveness of response to different emerging threats in Europe;
- Preparedness plan/plans to respond to potential emerging threats in Europe connected to animal-, food-, water- or environment transmission.

Topic ET-5: Ecology of emerging pathogens

Context

In order to prevent and control emerging pathogens that are zoonotic and foodborne, knowledge about pathogen transmission between human and animal populations and the environment is essential. This includes knowledge about disease dynamics within populations, and the interface between populations (human, livestock, or wildlife) and the environment.

Objectives

Studies may focus on both emerging and re-emerging pathogens, including currently unknown hazards, and should include as much as possible the following objectives:

- Identify determinants of spread and persistence of foodborne zoonoses in wildlife

reservoirs or the environment

- Investigate factors (and links between these) that may favour the emergence of foodborne zoonoses, e.g. pathogen virulence, global trade with food and foodstuffs, high population densities and degree of contact between populations (animal-animal, food-human, human- animal)
- Develop, parameterise and use disease spread models that capture transmission within and between relevant parts of the ecological system (e.g. human-animal, domestic animals-wildlife, human or animals-environment, or pathogen-individual-herd-population)
- Understand the role of mobile genetic elements in the ecology and emergence of new pathogens
- Use molecular epidemiology to study host dynamics and to reconstruct high resolution transmission trees
- Assess the importance of transmission pathways across the ecological system
- Investigate transmission links and spatiotemporal trends of cases of emerging disease

Expected results

- Identification of transmission routes and potential interface of disease spread across parts of the ecological system
- Improved ability to optimise surveillance and disease control
- Identification of data requirements and knowledge gaps in the ecology of emerging pathogens
- Identification of host-pathogen-ecology-combinations that constitute a higher risk if pathogens are introduced

Theme RISK ASSESSMENT

Topic FBZ-9: Frameworks and systems for sharing tools and data for risk assessment and effective decision making

Context

Within and outside Europe, a large number of predictive modelling and risk assessment models, software tools and databases have been developed in the past decades. However, their maintenance is not always guaranteed and exchange of information between these resources is currently difficult and time consuming, which limits their application. An obvious next step is to combine the data and software tools that are available in Europe and facilitate the communication between them and the networks hosted by EFSA.

Objectives

The overall objective is to facilitate the shared use of existing risk assessment tools and knowledge bases in Europe, to allow harmonised, fast and effective decision support in Europe.

- to create a cross domain inventory of existing risk assessment and data resources; (link to integrative topics 4 and 5)
- to create and apply a shared language that allows communication between these tools; (link to integrative topic 4)
- to extend and improve shared infrastructures (data standards, controlled vocabularies/ domain- specific ontologies, open source software code) that support the bridging of existing risk assessment and data resources of the EJP partners; (link to

integrative topic 4)

- to enhance existing tools / database/ resources, to facilitate the seamless exchange of information between these tools; (link to integrative topic 5 and 7)
- to establish a pan European harmonised data collection and freely accessible data; (link to integrative topic 5)
- to perform demonstration and dissemination activities to showcase the successful proof-of- concept implementation;

Expected results

- Established shared infrastructure to integrate and exchange risk assessment models facilitating easy access and optimum use of existing decision support tools and newly created knowledge bases. (link to integrative topic 5 and 7)
- Evidence for added value of the common infrastructure by proof-of-concept applications in the form of prototypic examples of the implementation of an EJP knowledge base created through between-partner sharing of existing tools and models.
- Core results of the project are joint use of harmonized standards by EJP partner organisations and the joint infrastructure that provides resources that will be of immediate and future practical use when performing risk assessment to support decision making in Europe. (link to integrative topics 4, 5 and 7)

Topic AMR-5: Disease burden, socio-economic consequences and risk ranking

Context

Disease burden is increasingly studied, particularly to inform risk management strategies. The recent publications on the global disease burden of foodborne disease have shown the relevance and potential of quantitative disease burden estimation, among others as a basis for risk prioritization. These latest developments also highlighted current challenges in estimating the burden of some foodborne diseases, particularly associated with AMR and other emerging threats. Due to the complex transmission and health consequences, these require further method development, for which for example new generation sequencing typing offers new opportunities. Furthermore, the need to extend current burden of disease estimations by incorporating socio economic consequences is widely recognized. By integrating health, economic and social impact assessments (applying e.g. multi-criteria decision analysis), and develop a method that can be applied in different countries, comparative risk rankings can be performed across the EU.

Objectives

- Develop models to estimate the burden of disease associated with AMR determinants and pathogens, for example by making use of available NGS data.
- Develop a general multi-criteria framework for decision making that can take into account different factors like human and animal health burden, environmental impact, as well as socio- economic factors and allows for a harmonised risk ranking approach across Europe.
- Develop risk ranking methods and perform risk ranking for foodborne diseases, including pathogens, viruses, parasites, AMR determinants and bacteria, as well as emerging threats, applying this general multi-criteria decision framework.

Expected results

- Development of models to estimate the burden of disease of AMR determinants and

- zoonotic pathogens of relevance in the EU in animal and human populations.
- Development of harmonised risk ranking methods for FBZ, AMR and ET;
 - Disease burden estimates and risk ranking of foodborne diseases, including AMR determinants and bacteria and other pathogens in different European countries;
 - Multi-criteria risk ranking applied in several case studies for FBZ, AMR and ET.

Topic ET-3: Applying risk assessment/modelling methodologies to support decisions for the control of emerging threats, foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance

Context

In the past decades, risk assessment modelling has been developed and applied in a number of European countries, mainly for microbial hazards like *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and *Listeria*. As a next step, it is important to further develop and apply risk assessment methods in the area of foodborne zoonoses and for a broader range of hazards, including emerging threats, antimicrobial resistant bacteria, viruses and parasites. These risk assessments should be aimed at decision support, including cost benefit analyses, cross- border animal movement and trade with feed and food.

Objectives

- To develop a decision support framework for the different cases (foodborne zoonoses, emerging threats, AMR, animal disease, etc.) to inform what types of assessments are needed
- To further develop relevant novel risk assessment methods for adequate, rapid and fit for purpose decision support for the control of emerging threats, foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance, taking advantage of novel methods for identification and characterization of hazards.
- To perform international risk assessment case studies, including cross national animal movement and trade with feed and food.
- To strengthen the collaboration between EJP partners in the area of risk assessment, by building shared tools and harmonising data collection (link to integrative topics 4 and 5)

Expected results

- The project will provide novel risk assessment toolboxes for EJP partners, provide capacity building between them and strengthen the tools for rapid decision support. (link to integrative topics 4 and 5)
- Novel risk assessment methods that allow the inclusion of NGS and metagenomic data, as well as improved hazard characterisation.
- Novel risk assessment tools for specific microbial hazards (e.g. *Toxoplasma*), emerging threats (e.g. models for their introduction and spread, and the impact of reactions to early detection) and the spread of antimicrobial resistance
- Specific relevant pan-European risk assessments performed to support control of emerging threats, foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance.

Theme INTERVENTION

Topic FBZ-3: Biosecurity and other interventions

Context

Introduction, transmission, development and accumulation of zoonotic pathogens, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats in humans and animals must be detected and prevented as early as possible using suitable approaches, tools and interventions. Biosecurity (the sum of preventive measures to keep the unwanted microbes away from animals/humans/food/feed) is one of the key interventions as “prevention is better than cure”.

Due to the large differences in production systems across the Med Vet sectors and countries, and taking into account the developing and changing husbandry and climate, routes of infection, different terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems and niches, food production and behavioral patterns, the optimal solution in one area might not be optimal in another. It is important to validate promising practices in different countries and to perform robust, meaningful studies to provide sound evidence and avoid wasting funds on studies of insufficient power. It is also necessary to find the best ways to communicate such complex matters. As there are many microbes and problems of interest and relevance, it is important to have a broad perspective, including problems not much studied earlier.

Objectives

The overall aim is to enable authorities, the industry, veterinarians and medical doctors to take the best actions possible to prevent, or reduce as early and as much as possible, the negative consequences of food borne pathogens, emerging diseases and antimicrobial resistance. This will be achieved by providing the European community (authorities, industry) with better and more harmonized interventions and codes of best practices and a “toolbox” in case there is a need to take actions against various threats. The research will focus on pathogens of EU priority as supported by EU level prioritisation exercises, strategic research agendas or similar.

Specific aims:

- To identify and benchmark best practice systems for efficient and cost-effective biosecurity in farms, feed- and food processing units and hospitals. Other interventions to be considered can include surveillance and/or control programs, vaccination, phages, pro- or prebiotics, disinfectants, prevention of biofilm, interventions at microbial level, optimizing husbandry, food processing and medical care procedures, feeding practices and the impact on commensal microbiotas and their competitive exclusion of pathogenic agents both to reduce the burden of disease and minimizing the use of antimicrobials.
- Develop tools to evaluate cost effectiveness of interventions, and tools to evaluate the effectiveness of implemented interventions.
- To develop and evaluate novel tools for collecting and communicating data and information and for education of and communication with farmers, industry and health care workers.

Expected results

- Easily available best practice guides and scoring/evaluation systems for biosecurity measures for different production systems and stakeholders to be used as a decision support system (link to integrative topic 6).
- An easily accessible database of threats and possible interventions in different situations, including the cost effectiveness of such interventions (link to integrative topic 6).
- New intervention methods and systems for evaluation of the effectiveness of

implemented interventions.

Topic FBZ-6: Risk communication and consumer targeted intervention strategies

Context

Foodborne zoonotic pathogens constitute an important European problem, and prevention of such diseases would lead to improvement of human health and economic benefits. Due to globalization and various selective pressures, pathogens on the European market are likely to have changed in recent years, and changing production systems create new challenges relating to pathogens in locally and globally produced food. Not all relevant pathogens can be removed before they reach the consumers, making it a necessity to look for possible interventions at consumer level and to educate consumers about possible risks.

Objectives

The overall aim is to enable consumers, authorities, the industry and the health care systems to take the best actions and interventions possible to prevent or reduce the negative consequences of food borne pathogens. Give the European community (authorities, industry) a “toolbox” regarding communication and consumer targeted interventions. The research should be focussed on pathogens of EU priority as supported by EU level prioritisation exercises, strategic research agendas or similar.

Specific aims:

- To identify the knowledge gaps, both internationally and nationally, to identify the most optimal consumer targeted interventions, and to evaluate the efficacy of the intervention strategies regarding effect on the consumers as well as barriers to their acceptance. (link to integrative topic 6)
- To investigate how to eliminate/reduce food borne pathogens in hosts/environments including possibilities to modify or change the human gut flora or immunity, e.g. by dietary strategies, prebiotics etc
- To study the most effective strategies for knowledge transfer and risk communication to the consumers, including the motivation and maintenance of awareness and compliance.

Expected results

- Increased capacity in the field of Risk communication in the participating institutions and countries. (link to integrative topic 6)
- Increased knowledge on national/regional differences in regards to communication with consumers regarding food borne risks and how to deal with such differences. (link to integrative topic 6)

Topic FBZ-7: Optimizing options for risk management and enforcement in feed and food production and processing

Context

Foodborne zoonotic pathogens constitute an important European problem, and prevention of such diseases would lead to improvement of human health and economic benefits. In addition to various aspects linked to managing prevalence and growth of food-borne pathogens, the international trade in feed, foods and breeding animals might constitute additional challenges when it comes to risk management options.

Objectives

The overall aim is to provide European authorities and the feed and food industries with effective risk management options for prevention and/or reduction of the negative consequences of food borne pathogens.

Specific aims:

- To identify, assess and quantify risks, and to evaluate the cost benefit of various intervention methods.
- To optimize various processing steps.
- To evaluate the efficacy of various communication strategies.

Expected results

- Guidelines and/or regulations regarding consumption, trade, usage of feed and feed materials and interventions (control measures and/or treatment strategies) in the food chain for optimal risk management. (link to integrative topic 6)
- Cost benefit analyses relating to routine analysis and decisions on actions in commercial production.
- Improved ability to interpret results obtained with molecular detection methods with respect to quantifying risk and possible false positives/negatives, pathogenic/non-pathogenic, viable/non-viable strains.
- Easily accessible blueprints for improved HACCP plans in food processing.

Topic AMR-4: Communication and Stewardship AMR

Context

Communication with stakeholders and stewardship of antimicrobial usage form an important component of the strategy to combat antimicrobial resistance and preserve the effectiveness of antimicrobials in both man and animals. The responsible use of antimicrobials in animals is promoted at the national level in European countries, as well at the European level, for example by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and European Platform for Responsible Use of Medicines in Animals (EPRUMA). The development of robust, evidence-based guidelines in animals is not however as advanced as in man. Interventions to improve prescribing practices and develop optimal communication strategies in animals are required, as well as the development of interventions (guidelines and advice) based on a robust evidence-base, which consider the principles developed in human medicine and those issues specific to animals. The impact of different prescribing practices in both animals and man on the development of antimicrobial resistance is a component of the evidence-base on which appropriate interventions may be recommended.

Objectives

- Development of robust, evidence-based, antimicrobial stewardship guidelines for animals.
- Provision of detailed case or scenario studies, providing examples of successful or beneficial outcomes in relation to selected animal disease conditions.
- Collaboration between medical and veterinary sectors to assimilate best practice developed in human medicine into veterinary medicine (link to integrative topic 6).
- Determining the most effective routes of communication with stakeholders, and influencing stakeholder behavior to promote responsible use.
- Development of systems to monitor adverse consequences of adoption of

antimicrobial stewardship guidelines including negative effects on animal productivity, welfare or costs of production.

Expected results

- Development of evidence-based antimicrobial stewardship guidelines for animals.
- Cross-collaboration between medical and veterinary specialists to optimize stewardship guidelines (link to integrative topic 6).
- A repository of case / scenario studies providing practical examples of beneficial outcomes.
- Identification of the optimal routes of communication with stakeholders.
- Clear identification of adverse consequences.

APPENDIX F: Report on the gap analysis of first round topics

Report on the gap analysis of first round priority topics

Objectives

As a first step of the procedure for updating the research and integrative topics of the Strategic Research Agenda (SRA), a gap analysis to identify first round topics insufficiently covered by the granted projects was performed in collaboration with the SRA domain and theme secretaries. Topics that are sufficiently covered will not be included in the second round of project proposals.

The specific objectives of this gap analysis are:

- To identify gaps between the objectives of the selected priority (research and integrative) topics and the objectives of the respective projects granted at the first round.
- To assess the overall coverage of the SRA by the first round topics.
- To propose inputs needed to close the identified gaps.
- To propose a list of insufficiently covered first round topics to be (re)included in the prioritization/selection process for the second round of project proposals.

This report presents the results of the gap analysis to be validated by the Project Management Team (PMT).

Procedure

In total, 8 priority research topics and 2 priority integrative topics have been assessed. These were the topics selected for the first OHEJP call for project proposals. Within these topics, a total of 11 joint research projects and 2 joint integrative projects have been granted. An overview of the topics and projects is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Overview of the first round topics (and related projects) included in this gap analysis.

Research topics		Projects
FBZ-1	Improved surveillance system and harmonized data analyses	NOVA
FBZ-2	Development and harmonization of NGS-based methods for detection and tracing of FBZ agents, emerging threats and AMR determinants	METASTAVA; ListAdapt
FBZ-3	Biosecurity and other interventions	AIR SAMPLE; MoMIR-PPC
FBZ-4	Source attribution and transmission routes	MedVetKlebs
AMR-1	Development and harmonization of phenotypic methods	IMPART
AMR-2	Epidemiological studies into the dynamics of AMR in human and animals populations and the environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR	ARDIG
AMR-3	Risk assessment of AMR	RADAR
ET-1	Development and harmonisation of non-NGS-based methods for detection of FBZ agents and emerging threats	Tox-detect; MAD-VIR
Integrative topics		Projects
IT-4	Standardised data formats and ontologies, common tools and procedures for data analyses, incl. interpretation of sequence data	ORION

IT-5	Common reporting and signalling procedures, joint platform for sharing surveillance data and their interpretation, incl. risk assessments	COHESIVE
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The gap analysis was coordinated by the WP2 team. The 5 theme and 3 domain secretaries were asked to contribute to the gap analysis of the research topics, whereas for the priority integrative topics, the WP4 leader (A. Lindberg) and deputy leader (M. Caniça) were involved. Each of the 8 priority research topics was then assessed by 2 secretaries, i.e. the respective domain and theme secretaries of each topic as per Table 2.

Table 2. One Health EPJ strategic matrix showing the 5 theme and 3 domain secretaries along with the topics they assessed in this gap analysis.

	DOMAINES		
THEMES	Foodborne zoonoses (FBZ) <i>K. Krogfelt</i>	Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) <i>J.Y. Madec</i>	Emerging threats (ET) <i>D. Horton</i>
Analytical methods <i>S. Morabito</i>	FBZ-2	AMR-1	ET-1
Host-microbe interaction <i>B. Gonzalez-Zorn</i>			
Epidemiology <i>D. Wasyl</i>	FBZ-1 FBZ-4	AMR-2	
Risk assessment <i>M. Nauta</i>		AMR-3	
Intervention <i>M. Hofshagen</i>	FBZ-3		

As no topic within the theme “Host-microbe interaction” was selected in the first round, B. Gonzalez-Zorn was excused to participate in the assessments. The other assessors were provided by the WP2 team with pre-compiled assessment sheets summarizing: 1) the list of objectives (or expected results in case their description in the SRA was more detailed than the one of the objectives) of each selected topic, and 2) the list of objectives (or of expected results in case their description was more detailed than the one of the objectives) of each granted project therein. Although both the topic and project objectives were schematically reported in the assessment sheets to ease their assessment, the assessors were also invited to always refer to the SRA and to the full project proposals. The assessment sheets are appended to this report. The assessment of the topics was performed as follows:

- 1. Comparison between the topic and project objectives.** The topic objectives formed the “desired future state”, i.e. where that specific priority topic wants to go to. Indeed, these objectives indicate what we want to have from the projects granted within this priority research topic. The project objectives formed the “current situation” instead, i.e. what we expect to obtain from that specific project.
- 2. Assess the coverage of the topic objectives by the project objectives.** Having compared what the priority topics aim to obtain from the projects and what the granted projects are on due course to provide, each assessor was asked to score the overall level of coverage of the topic

objectives based on the expected input from the granted projects. The scoring system was based on the following criteria:

Poor (P)	Substantial essential information/data is still required to fully address most topic objectives, and this information/data will not be provided by the granted projects
Fair (F)	Granted projects are generally able to address most topic objectives, with some major additional information/data still needed
Good (G)	Granted projects are fully able to address all or most topic objectives, with very minor additional information/data still needed
Excellent (E)	Granted projects will fully address all topic objectives (special mention)

3. **Justify the assessments and indicate inputs needed to fill the gaps.** Having determined the level of coverage of a given topic, the assessor was invited to provide brief comments in support of the assessment and to indicate which inputs are still needed to fill the gaps, i.e. the inputs needed to fully address all topic objectives.

The assessors therefore returned their assessment sheets to the WP2 team for analysis to: 1) check for conflicting assessments between the two assessors of a given topic; 2) summarize the topic assessments by coverage; and 3) summarize the input needs to fill the gaps in coverage. In the event of conflicting assessments, a consensus between the assessors was reached before or during the secretaries meeting held at Schiphol Airport on the 20th of April; the WP2 team acted herein as mediator. At consensus meeting, the domain and theme secretaries had the opportunity to present and discuss altogether the assessments, to agree on the scores, gaps and inputs needs identified for each topic, and to prepare a list of insufficiently covered first round topics. Moreover, through extensive discussions during the meeting, a number of “research areas” falling within the scope of OHEJP, but being underrepresented in the SRA and in the granted projects, were also identified and reported here.

Results

All 9 assessors involved in the gaps analysis completed and returned their assessments. Consensus on the scores for the coverage was reached for all topics. The secretaries meeting was attended by D. Wasyl, M. Nauta, M. Hofshagen, K. Krogfelt, D. Horton, and by M. Caniça via Skype (for the most part of it), as well as the WP2 team (A. van der Giessen, L. Mughini-Gras, M. Bouwknecht, L. de Juan). As consensus, topic FBZ-3 was assessed as being poorly covered, and topics FBZ-4, AMR-2 and ET-1 as being fairly covered, by the granted projects. Topics FBZ-1, FBZ-2, and AMR-2 received a “good” coverage score, and topics AMR-1, IT-4 and IT-5 an “excellent” score. An overview of the coverage scores for each topic is showed in Table 3.

Table 3. Overview of the coverage scores of each first round topic.

Topic	Score assessor 1	Score assessor 2	Consensus
FBZ-1	Good	Good	Good
FBZ-2	Good	Fair	Good
FBZ-3	Fair	Poor	Poor
FBZ-4	Fair	Good	Fair

AMR-1	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent
AMR-2	Fair	Fair	Fair
AMR-3	Good	Good	Good
ET-1	Fair	Fair	Fair
IT-4	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent
IT-5	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent

A number of gaps and input needs were also identified; these are summarized, topic by topic in Table 4.

Table 4. Overview of the topic objectives and gaps/input needs identified. The colours of the text in the table indicate the level of coverage of each topic's objectives: **blue** → objective sufficiently covered; **yellow** → objective partly covered; **red** → objective insufficiently covered.

Topic	Topic objectives*	Input needs
FBZ-1	<p>The study should perform research that enables new surveillance approaches or facilitates evaluation and comparison of the cost-effectiveness of different surveillance systems. This may include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assessments of the effects of focusing surveillance resources by using risk-based or consequence-based approaches 2. Assessments of potential benefit from targeted surveillance across the food chain and humans 3. Modelling of surveillance activities, based on existing or simulated population data, and exploration of potential new surveillance strategies 4. Development and evaluation of syndromic surveillance systems, and use of novel data sources 5. Estimation of the effect of applying harmonized pathogen/case nomenclature between countries, or animals and humans (e.g. in whole-genome sequencing for definition of cases), on surveillance design and performance <p>The project should also address the development of improved surveillance approaches (i.e. new types, approaches, novel methods). It should cover as much as possible specific aspects of the following issues in surveillance systems:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Propose new and/or improved types, approaches, and/or methods of surveillance 2. Selection and spread of antimicrobial resistance in relation to antimicrobial usage and residues (within One Health approach), and/or 3. Relate surveillance outcomes to public and animal health consequences (disease burden within One Health approach), 4. Facilitate communication (early-warning, common definitions) and timely sharing of surveillance data between partner laboratories. (link to integrative topic 5) 5. The research will focus on zoonotic agents of EU priority as supported by EU level prioritisation exercises, strategic research agendas or similar. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better pan-EU representation, specifically societal differences and access to/usage of technology (credit/debit card receipts, social media, internet, etc.) among MSs. • Data quality and reliability regarding potential geographical bias. • FBZ agents underlying the target of syndromic surveillance systems need to be more explicitly given. • Ex post/ante facto effects of applying harmonized pathogen/case/animal nomenclature between countries on surveillance performance. • Improved surveillance systems relating AMU and AMR (for FBZ) and those relating surveillance outcomes to animal/human disease burden.
FBZ-2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Harmonized procedures for sample preparation, DNA-isolation, library preparation and sequencing, including the assessment of quality parameters achievable with the different platforms for NGS (research objective – link with integrative topic 2 and 3) 2. The establishment of standardized and validated pipelines to extract information from raw NGS data on the detection and typing of specific pathogens, and genomic traits in genomes including virulence genes and AMR determinants (research objective - link with integrative topic 4) 3. The identification of specific pathogens, potential emerging threats, in microbiota 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmonization and standardization of procedures need to be improved to make sure that, e.g., NGS methods work the same way everywhere. Ring or proficiency tests involving mainly medical institutes (if not addressed by other projects/initiatives like COMPARE, or by EURLs or GMI) should be promoted. • Developed methodologies need validation, e.g. by applying them in the field, also as diagnostic tools.

	<p>of complex specimens through culture-independent metagenomics (research objective – to be tuned with research topic AMR 10).</p>	
FBZ-3	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> To identify and benchmark best practice systems for efficient and cost-effective biosecurity in farms, feed- and food processing units and hospitals. Other interventions to be considered can include surveillance and/or control programs, vaccination, phages, pro- or prebiotics, disinfectants, prevention of biofilm, interventions at microbial level, optimizing husbandry, food processing and medical care procedures, feeding practices and the impact on commensal microbiotas and their competitive exclusion of pathogenic agents both to reduce the burden of disease and minimizing the use of antimicrobials. Develop tools to evaluate cost effectiveness of interventions, and tools to evaluate the effectiveness of implemented interventions. To develop and evaluate novel tools for collecting and communicating data and information and for education of and communication with farmers, industry and health care workers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tools for evaluating cost-effectiveness of biosecurity measures along the farm-to-fork continuum, and in healthcare settings, need to be addressed more explicitly. Except for pro- or prebiotics, other interventions including but not limited to biosecurity need to be addressed. Identification and benchmarking of biosecurity measures need to be performed on the whole food production chain. Biosecurity aspects in human medicine need to be addressed. Tools to educate/communicate to farmers, industry, healthcare, etc. need to be developed.
FBZ-4	<p>The study should:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> focus on food- and water-borne pathogens, either bacteria, viruses, fungi, parasites, as well as antimicrobial resistance and its transmissible elements, prioritized by EU level prioritisation exercises, strategic research agendas or similar aim at identification of reservoirs, sources, vehicles, and routes of pathogen transmission applying a One Health approach impose ecological approach, not limited to farm-to-fork concept, food of animal origin, or animal to human transmission. Instead, the role of environment, wildlife and non-food producing animals, globalisation (imports, travels, etc.), and/or human behaviour is anticipated, address human impact on ecology of pathogens and antimicrobial resistance, to involve both conventional and novel (NGS-based) techniques, develop or improve pipelines or models for source attribution, to critically assess and improve existing models for source attribution facilitate an integrated approach between source and outcome by data sharing. (link to integrative topic 5) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other pathogens (besides Klebsiella), as well as AMR, need to be addressed by source attribution, i.e. the scope needs to be expanded to include other FBZs, specifically viruses, parasites and fungi. Pan-EU data quality and reliability need to be addressed. The points of attribution (reservoir, source, vehicle, route) need to cover the whole transmission chain (farm-to-fork) and beyond (ecological approach - e.g. imports, travels, etc.) to identify multiple targets for preventive and control measures. Development of new (and/or improvement of existing) pipelines and models for source attribution needs to be addressed. Sharing of data for source attribution needs to be addressed.
AMR-1	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Rapid and cheap, high-performing, harmonized diagnostic solutions for targeted antimicrobial treatment in humans and animals. New antibiotic-enriched selective culture media which allow rapid screening of emergent resistant phenotypes and that are not covered by the existing market (colistin, aminoglycosides, ...) are developed. Validated data on new and existing antimicrobial susceptibility testing methods brought to clinical practice in human or veterinary medicine, or to laboratories 	None

	<p>analysing food samples.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Epidemiological cut-off values and clinical breakpoints for selected antimicrobial/pathogen combinations are determined Link to integrative topic 2: Harmonized methods for generating comparable data of AMR in humans, animals, feed, food and the environment are available. 	
AMR-2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Investigate geographical differences and trends in antimicrobial usage and resistance in the environment, human (including exposure groups) and animal populations, based on current, available monitoring programmes in the EU. Study the influence of animal management (including antimicrobial usage) on the occurrence and spread of resistance, Clarify associations between consequences of antimicrobial usage and levels and spread of resistance; develop appropriate methodologies. Study associations between antimicrobial usage and resistance in bacteria from food animals, companion animals and humans Study associations between resistance mechanisms in bacteria of environmental, animal and human origin, Special attention should be paid to multidrug and emerging resistances, as well as resistance to critically important antimicrobials for human and animal treatment, Study the origin and transmission dynamics of resistant bacteria (i.e. import versus local selection, zoonotic versus anthropogenic versus environmental) Study clonal spread of resistant bacteria versus horizontal gene transfer in the dissemination of resistance within One Health approach. These might include fitness cost studies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pan-EU perspective (particularly geographical differences in AMU/AMR between West-East or North-South Europe). Associations between AMU (in animals/humans) and AMR dynamics need to be addressed in a more direct way using study designs based on control and exposed groups in different countries. Some POs should be verified against other projects like EFFORTS to check whether the TOs are all covered. Study the origin and transmission of AMR, incl. horizontal gene transfer, within One Health approach.
AMR-3	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Improved understanding of the association between antimicrobial use and resistance. Tools to predict microbial development (survival and transmission) through the food chain, including the effect of processing steps. Generic RA-models applicable and adaptable to various AMR determinants. Increased understanding of the role of the environment in dissemination of antimicrobial resistance and human exposure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of a platform for sharing RA models needs to be addressed (suggestion for IT?) Environmental component needs to be addressed more explicitly.
ET-1	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> The development of approaches for the pheno/genotypic (non-NGS-based) detection of new zoonotic agents and emerging threats covering all the process from sampling to sample preparation and analysis of results (research objective). The development of rapid and reliable non-NGS-based tools for the detection of new zoonotic agents and emerging threats at bed/pen/farm-site or other locations in the food production chain (research objective). The optimisation and validation of existing and newly developed methods for the pheno/genotypic (non-NGS-based) detection of new zoonotic agents and emerging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focus needs to be extended to microorganisms other than just viruses and toxigenic bacteria. New sampling techniques/strategies need to be developed, including application of microarray technology --- The project "AirSample" within topic FBZ-3 covers the TO of new sampling techniques and on-site collection. New farm/bed/pen tests need to be developed. Possible overlap with EURL mandates need to be addressed in assessment of future proposals.

	threats (research objective- in collaboration with integrative topic 3).	
IT-4	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. To carry out an inventory of the current practice with regard to data collection and methods for interpretation of surveillance data (including epidemiological and microbiological data; also sequence data).2. To perform a terminology mapping to create a semantic network between the different systems. Creation of an initial map to link different terminologies/thresholds. Work with the stakeholders to resolve the ambiguous and unmapped items.3. To provide an overall architecture of a surveillance programme (guidelines) with the highest level of harmonization with either international standards, if available, or a uniform approach to collection, management and analysis of data that acknowledges the requirements for national reporting to relevant EU bodies.	None
IT-5	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. To conduct an inventory of existing joint platforms within partner institutes and at EU level, used for sharing and visualising surveillance data, including horizon scanning information, nationally and internationally, launching early warning and conducting risk assessments.2. To support alignment with existing EU initiatives (EFSA, ECDC) for communication of surveillance data.3. To facilitate transfer of experiences with early warning and risk assessment across MS and across the Med-Vet interface, by identifying context-specific best-practice.4. To analyse the existing systems to propose the best practice to define baselines, to detect signals, and to communicate to stakeholders and the public.	None

Conclusions

Based on the results of the gap analysis, the following 4 topics were considered as being insufficiently covered and therefore proposed by the secretaries for (re)inclusion in the prioritization procedure for the second round of project proposals:

1. FBZ-3 Biosecurity and other interventions.
2. FBZ-4 Source attribution and transmission routes.
3. AMR-2 Epidemiological studies into the dynamics of AMR in human and animals populations and the environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR.
4. ET-1 Development and harmonisation of non-NGS-based methods for detection of FBZ agents and emerging threats.

Besides these topics, there were 3 “research areas” identified by the secretaries as being underrepresented in the SRA:

1. Role of the natural environment in human and animal health and disease
2. Human/animal waste management and associated health risks
3. Resistance against antifungal and antiparasitic drugs

The secretaries also identified 4 “research areas” being underrepresented in the granted projects:

1. Parasite research
2. Virus research
3. Host-pathogen interactions
4. Risk assessment

At the 1-day meeting with the PMT on the 11th of May, the results of this analysis were discussed and consolidated.

APPENDIX G: Summary of national priorities per general topic

GENERAL INFORMATION

This document contains suggestions to narrow down the research topics based on the national research priorities expressed by the OH-EJP partner institutes. The keywords of these priorities have been visually summarized in word clouds, each one per topic to be narrowed down. The experts are asked to consider these suggestions when narrowing down the research topics linked to the original (broad) topics. The font size of the words in the clouds is increased proportionally to the times a word occurs over all national research priorities, thereby representing a way to identify the most represented research input needs across all the countries participating to OH-EJP.

NB. This is only 1 of 4 sources of information provided to the experts to support the narrow down procedure of the research topics. Narrowed down topics do not necessarily have to include all these needs, and the same need does not necessarily have to be included multiple times in different topics. Needs that will not be addressed by the narrowed down topics will proceed as individual topics to the prioritization.

Theme ANALYTICAL METHODS

Topic AMR-6: Metagenomics and bioinformatics for detection and surveillance of AMR pathogens and determinants

Theme HOST-MICROBE INTERACTION

Topic FBZ-8: Model Systems (in vitro and in vivo) to study host/food – microbe interactions

Topic FBZ-5: Epidemiological studies: risk factors and dynamics

Topic AMR-2: Epidemiological studies into the dynamics of AMR in human and animal populations and the environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR

Topic ET-2: Improving preparedness and response

Topic ET-5: Ecology of emerging pathogens

Theme RISK ASSESSMENT

Topic FBZ-9: Frameworks and systems for sharing tools and data for risk assessment and effective decision making

Topic AMR-5: Disease burden, socio-economic consequences and risk ranking

Topic ET-3: Applying risk assessment/modelling methodologies to support decisions for the control of emerging threats, foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance

Topic FBZ-6: Risk communication and consumer targeted intervention strategies

Topic FBZ-7: Optimizing options for risk management and enforcement in feed and food production and processing

Topic AMR-4: Communication and Stewardship AMR

APPENDIX H: European stakeholders' needs

GENERAL INFORMATION

This document contains suggestions to narrow down the research topics based on research needs expressed by the European stakeholders (EFSA, ECDC and DG SANTE). Specific needs have been placed in the OHEJP matrix to facilitate their identification when narrowing down topics falling within specific research areas; the experts are asked to consider these suggestions when narrowing down the research topics linked to the respective research areas in the matrix.

NB. This is only 1 of 4 sources of information provided to the experts to support the narrow down procedure of the research topics. Narrowed down topics do not necessarily have to include all these needs, and the same need does not necessarily have to be included multiple times in different topics. Selected needs that will not be addressed by the narrowed down topics will proceed as individual topics to the prioritization.

DOMAINS

THEMES	Foodborne zoonoses (FBZ)	Antimicrobial resistance (AMR)	Emerging threats (ET)
Analytical methods	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Development of efficient and optimized cell culture methods for HEV (reproducibility and sensitivity). 2. To determine correlation of HEV RNA detection with infectivity of the virus. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Development of new tools for early (real-time) detection of resistant pathogens in humans and animals as well as new diagnostic tools in particular on-site tests in humans and animals. 	
Host-microbe interaction			
Epidemiology	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To explore (molecular) epidemiology of <i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> and <i>Y. pseudotuberculosis</i>. 2. To explore molecular epidemiology of foodborne yersiniosis, covering both biotype and serotype data from human yersiniosis cases, from food animals, and from foodborne outbreaks. 3. International aspects of <i>T. gondii</i> as foodborne pathogen. 4. To improve data generation/collection/sequencing on prevalence and concentration of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> in RTE foods and human cases. 5. Risk of transmission of HEV from contaminated water to food. 6. To improve data generation/collection/sequencing for Shiga toxin-producing <i>Escherichia coli</i> (STEC) infections in humans and occurrence/prevalence in foods and animals, also addressing global epidemiology and the fact that more and more hybrid STEC strains continue to pop up. 7. To develop network science (static and dynamic network analysis tools for various data sources) and mathematical modelling – as decision support tools – to enhance consumers' safety and the supply chain itself, to support crisis prevention, risk-based control, early warning and predictive systems. 8. Development of a methodological framework capable of simulating different epidemiological situations and connecting animal population networks to the human population network for the best disease modelling possible, to detect subtle changes of the animal trade and movement network and their impact, to increase preparedness for real epidemics, using network-based spreading models and to make an earlier and better intervention possible. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To assess the role of the environment in the transmission of AMR, taking into account that food animals and farming are not the only source of contamination of the environment with antimicrobials and antimicrobial-resistant microorganisms 2. Fill data gaps for antimicrobial resistance (e.g. ESBL <i>E. coli</i>, <i>mcr-1</i> carrying <i>E. coli</i>, <i>Salmonella</i> spp., <i>Campylobacter</i>, MRSA, resistance to last line antimicrobials) and assess the role of different transmission pathways (foodborne routes involving animal and non-animal foods, including information on country of origin), by water or other environmental contamination, through direct animal contact including pets and reptiles) and sources (e.g. foreign travel, other cross-contaminating products, machinery and the environment, as well as those workers who are producing and handling the meat product). 3. Investigate the role of sources other than poultry (e.g. wild birds, pets, environmental water, cattle) in selection or transmission of antimicrobial-resistant <i>C. jejuni</i> to humans. 4. Due to increasing detection and geographical dispersion of human LA-MRSA periodic systematic surveillance (including extended molecular testing to distinguish between 'human adapted' and 'livestock-adapted' clades of MRSA CC398) may be considered including veterinary sources to identify possible reservoirs/transmission pathways, providing useful information for prevention and control. 5. Understanding the epidemiology of AMR, in particular the pathways of transmission between animals and humans, and their impact. 6. Close knowledge gaps on the release of resistant microorganisms and antimicrobials into the environment and their spread 7. Research into and development of new tools for monitoring antimicrobials and microorganisms resistant against antimicrobials in the environment. 	

Risk Assessment

1. A rapid risk assessment tool integrating information on disease occurrence worldwide, pathways for introduction (e.g. trade, movements of people) and their related risks is needed to provide insight into the current and upcoming threats of emerging or re-emerging zoonotic and foodborne diseases for assessment of related risks, for risk management and early warning purposes.
2. To determine ways to collect large amounts of (big) data becoming available from primary production to a broad range of experts (e.g. veterinarians, food safety controllers, animal production specialists and data managers), to be used in the processing phase for risk assessment of the consumers.
3. To develop algorithms to relate large amount of data to food safety risks for humans, probably incorporating environmental factors around primary farms developing a One Health/Total Health quality system.

1. Explore risk assessment methodologies to evaluate the risks to human and animal health from the presence of antimicrobials in the environment.

Intervention

1. Determining the effectiveness of preventing exposure of humans and epidemiologically relevant animal species to known risk factors for *Toxoplasma gondii* infection.
2. Impact of vaccination and management methods of pig herds against HEV, and other options such as HEV-free pig herds.
3. Survival of HEV in meat products, bivalve molluscs, fruit and vegetables and their production and processing environment.
4. Conduct further research and evaluation on the source attribution model developed for EFSA for other pathogens, so that the results can be used for risk management decision support.
5. A need was identified on how to control efficiently *Salmonella* in pigs.
6. High-risk source regions and pathways needs to be identified by a rapid risk assessment tool to guide the implementation of preventive measures (e.g. by regulating imports of high-risk animals or products) and the design of targeted surveillance well ahead of time being able to prevent outbreaks and severe economic losses.
7. Food control should be targeted in relation to the risks for food safety on the basis of information from the food chain and less dependent on on-site control by quality controllers, leading to a system where "risk" animals are controlled on specific threats extensively.

1. Strengthened infection prevention and control measures, development of new effective preventive vaccines, development and assessment of interventions that prevent the development and spread of AMR.
2. Development of new economic models, exploring and analyzing incentives to boost the development of new therapeutics, alternatives, vaccines and diagnostics.
3. Development of technologies that enable efficient and rapid degradation of antimicrobials in wastewater and the environment and reduce the spread of AMR.

APPENDIX I: Gaps in the current work plan

GENERAL INFORMATION

This document contains suggestions to narrow down the research topics based on coverage of the objectives of the first round topics by the granted projects in the first round. This was part of the gap analysis carried out in WP2. Specific inputs have been placed in the OHEJP matrix to facilitate their identification when narrowing down topics falling within specific research areas; the experts are asked to consider these suggestions for existing gaps when narrowing down the research topics linked to the respective research areas in the matrix. More generic input that was received during the gap analysis, which in principle applies to multiple research areas in the matrix, is as follows: parasite and virus research, host-pathogen interactions, risk assessment, role of the natural environment in human and animal health, human and animal waste management and associated health risks, resistance to antifungal and antiparasitic drugs.

NB. This is only 1 of 4 sources of information provided to the experts to support the narrow down procedure of the research topics. Narrowed down topics do not necessarily have to include all these inputs, and the same input does not necessarily need to be included multiple times in different topics.

DOMAINES			
THEMES	Foodborne zoonoses (FBZ)	Antimicrobial resistance (AMR)	Emerging threats (ET)
Analytical methods			<p>Topic ET-1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More focus on microorganisms other than viruses and toxigenic bacteria. • Development of new sampling techniques/strategies, including application of microarray technology. • Development of new farm/bed/pen tests.
Host-microbe interaction			
Epidemiology	<p>Topic FBZ-4</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. More focus on source attribution of pathogens other than Klebsiella, specifically viruses, parasites and fungi, and on AMR. 2. Pan-EU data quality and reliability for source attribution. 3. The points of attribution (reservoir, source, vehicle, route) need to cover the whole transmission chain (farm-to-fork) and beyond (ecological approach - e.g. imports, travels, etc.) to identify multiple targets for preventive and control measures. 4. Development of new (and/or improvement of existing) pipelines and models for source attribution. 5. Sharing of data for source attribution. 	<p>Topic AMR-2</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pan-EU perspective (particularly geographical differences in AMU/AMR between West-East or North-South Europe). 2. Associations between AMU (in animals/humans) and AMR dynamics to be addressed in a direct way using study designs based on control and exposed groups in different countries. 3. Study the origin and transmission of AMR, incl. horizontal gene transfer, within the One Health approach. 	
Risk assessment			

Intervention

Topic FBZ-3

1. Tools for assessing cost-effectiveness of biosecurity measures along the farm-to-fork continuum, and in healthcare settings.
2. Except for pro- or prebiotics, other interventions including, but not limited to, biosecurity, need to be addressed.
3. Identification and benchmarking of biosecurity measures need to be performed on the whole food production chain.
4. Biosecurity aspects in human medicine.
5. Tools to educate/communicate to farmers, industry, healthcare, etc.

APPENDIX L: Other EU projects and initiatives

GENERAL INFORMATION

This document contains information on other EU projects and initiatives that link in some form to OHEJP, to support the narrow down process of the research topics by highlighting potential strategic interactions with the research activities carried out within a given (narrowed down) topics. These other EU projects/initiatives have been placed in the OHEJP matrix to facilitate their identification when narrowing down topics falling within specific research areas. Information sheets with essential information (as well as secondary sources for further consultation) for all projects are contained in this document as well. The experts are asked to consider possible interactions with these projects/initiatives when narrowing down the research topics linked to the respective research areas in the matrix.

NB. This is only 1 of 4 sources of information provided to the experts to support the narrow down procedure of the research topics. Narrowed down topics do not necessarily have to include all possible interactions with these projects, and the same interaction does not necessarily need to be included multiple times in different topics.

	DOMAINES		
THEMES	Foodborne zoonoses (FBZ)	Antimicrobial resistance (AMR)	Emerging threats (ET)
Analytical methods	COMPARE ENGAGE* INNUENDO GMI	EFFORT JPIAMR	COMPARE EMERGE VetBioNet GMI
Host-microbe interaction	ENGAGE*	EFFORT ENGAGE* JPIAMR	VetBioNet
Epidemiology	COMPARE INNUENDO	EFFORT JPIAMR	COMPARE
Risk assessment	COMPARE	EFFORT JPIAMR JAMRAI	COMPARE VetBioNet
Intervention		EFFORT JPIAMR JAMRAI	COMPARE VetBioNet

*Project finished

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Collaborative Management Platform for detection and Analyses of (Re-) emerging and foodborne outbreaks in Europe			
Acronym	COMPARE			
Website	http://www.compare-europe.eu/			
Coordinator's name	Frank Aarestrup			
Contact details	fmaa@food.dtu.dk; compare@food.dtu.dk			
Coordinator's Institution	Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Denmark			
Funding programme	European Union's Horizon 2020 Grant agreement 643476			
Duration	2014.12.01 – 2019.12.01			
Total budget	20.8 million			
Consortium^a	29 Partners, 11 countries			
	ANU (AUSTRALIA) UA (BE) FLI (DE) RKI (DE) EMBL (DE) CIVIC (DE) DSMZ (DE) UK-BONN (DE)	TIHO (DE) DTU (DK) SSI (DK) UCLM (ES) IFREMÉR (FR) ANSES (FR) FMER (FR) RT (FR)	AUTH (GR) WIGNER (HU) UNIBO (IT) ISS (IT) RIVM (NL) EMC (NL) AMC (NL) ARTEMIS (NL)	EUR (NL) DEFRA/APHA (UK) UEDIN (UK) UCAM (UK) WTSI (UK)
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To improve rapid identification, containment and mitigation of emerging infectious diseases and foodborne outbreaks. - To develop a cross-sector and cross-pathogen analytical framework and globally linked data and information-sharing platform. - To integrate state-of-the-art strategies, tools, technologies and methods for collecting, processing and analysing sequenced-based pathogen data in combination with associated data (clinical, epidemiological, and other). - To generate actionable information for relevant authorities and other users in the human health, animal health and food safety domains. 			
Work Packages	WP1. Risk assessment and risk-based strategies for sample and data collection. WP2. Harmonised standards for sample processing and sequencing. WP3. From comparable data to actionable information: Analytical workflows for frontline Diagnostics. WP4. From comparable data to actionable information: Analytical workflows for foodborne pathogen surveillance, outbreak detection and epidemiological analysis. WP5. From comparable data to actionable information: Additional tools for detection of and response to (re-) emerging infections. WP6. Underpinning research: Frontline diagnostics using the COMPARE analytical framework. WP7. Underpinning research on food outbreaks using the COMPARE analytical framework. WP8. Underpinning research: Novel approaches to (re-) emerging disease detection and			

	<p>outbreak response using the COMPARE analytical framework.</p> <p>WP9. COMPARE data and information platform.</p> <p>WP10. COMPARE risk communication tools.</p> <p>WP11. User consultations.</p> <p>WP12. Barriers to open data sharing.</p> <p>WP13. Dissemination and training.</p> <p>WP14. Cost-effectiveness framework.</p> <p>WP15. Management.</p>
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^a OHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Ecology from Farm to Fork of microbial drug Resistance and Transmission			
Acronym	EFFORT			
Website	http://www.effort-against-amr.eu			
Coordinator's name	Jaap A. Wagenaar			
Contact details	effort-office@eurtd.com			
Coordinator's Institution	Utrecht University (UUVU), The Netherlands			
Funding programme	European Union's FP7/2007-2013 Grant agreement 613754			
Duration	2013.12.01 – 2018.11.30			
Total budget	11,609,737.34 euros			
Consortium^a	19 partners, 10 countries			
	UGent (BE) Vetworks (BE) ILSI Europe (BE) NDVRI (BG) SAFOSO (CH)	TiHO (DE) BfR (DE) DTU (DK) Intomics (DK) UCM (ES)	ARTTIC (FR) ANSES (FR) IZSLT (IT) UUVU (NL) BEC (NL)	PorQ (NL) CVI (NL) VION FOOD (NL) PIWet (PL)
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understanding the epidemiology of AMR in the food chain. - Understanding the ecology of AMR in the microbial communities. - Understanding the relative contribution of the exposure routes of AMR from animals to humans. - Understanding the economic impact and animal welfare aspects of AMR in the food chain. 			
Work Packages	<p>WP1. Integrated evidence base for the food chain.</p> <p>WP2. Molecular approaches for determining the molecular ecology and epidemiology of antimicrobial resistance genes.</p> <p>WP3. Ecology and transfer of resistance mechanisms.</p> <p>WP4. Epidemiological analysis of antimicrobial resistance patterns in humans and the environment.</p> <p>WP5. Relationship between farming practices, antimicrobial usage, animal health and resistance.</p> <p>WP6. Intervention studies aiming at reducing antimicrobial usage and resistance in pigs and poultry production.</p> <p>WP7. Quantification of exposure to antimicrobial resistance through different transmission routes from animals to humans.</p> <p>WP8. Economic impact analysis.</p> <p>WP9. Project dissemination and training.</p> <p>WP10. Project management.</p>			

^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Establishing Next Generation sequencing Ability for Genomic analysis in Europe			
Acronym	ENGAGE			
Website	http://www.engage-europe.eu/			
Coordinator's name	Rene S. Hendriksen			
Contact details	rshe@food.dtu.dk			
Coordinator's Institution	Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Denmark			
Funding programme	European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) Grant agreement GP/EFSA/AFSCO/2015/01			
Duration	2016.01.29 – 2018.01.28			
Total budget				
Consortium^a	8 partners, 5 countries			
	BfR (DE) DTU (DK)	IZSve (IT) NIPH-NIH (PL)	NVRI (PL) IZSLT (IT)	PHE (UK) APHA (UK)
Objectives	<p>To establish collaboration between the public health, food and veterinary sectors across the European Union for building and enhancing the use of real-time whole genome sequencing and analysis in food safety and public health protection.</p> <p>The project will implement two joint “proof of concept” WGS projects to investigate: a) bacteria evolution and genetic diversity driven by genetic exchange, selection and clonal expansion; b) epidemiological relationships between the target microorganisms; c) identification of biologically successful clones; d) microbial determinants of virulence, antimicrobial resistance (AMR), and other putative markers in various emerging ‘epidemic’ strains of MDR <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Salmonella</i> having a strong impact in Europe</p> <p>The specific objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Two joint “proof of concept” WGS projects targeting emerging E.coli including VTEC and Salmonella lineages will be established among the consortium. - A cloud-based protected working space for sharing our genome data will be created. - Benchmarking of bioinformatic analytic tools. - Establish and conduct WGS proficiency tests. - Boost the scientific collaboration between scientists, clinicians, and risk assessors to exchange expertise and knowledge as well as to build capacity. 			
Work Packages	<p>WP1. Project cooperation framework.</p> <p>WP2. Data Collection.</p> <p>WP3. Whole genome sequencing.</p> <p>WP4. Genome database.</p> <p>WP5. Analysis / Benchmarking.</p> <p>WP6. Proficiency testing.</p> <p>WP7. Output / Outcome.</p> <p>WP8. Training / E-learning.</p> <p>WP9. Workshops.</p> <p>WP10. Dissemination.</p>			

^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Efficient response to highly dangerous and emerging pathogens at EU level			
Acronym	EMERGE			
Website	www.emerge.rki.eu			
Coordinator's name	Roland Grunow			
Contact details	grunowR@rki.de			
Coordinator's Institution	Robert Koch-Institute (RKI), Germany			
Funding programme	EU funded Joint Action (JA), Consumers, Health, Agriculture and Food Executive Agency (CHAFEA). Grant agreement 677066			
Duration	2015.06.01 – 2018.05.31			
Total budget	3,499,873 euros			
Consortium^a	33 partners, 22 countries			
	AGES (AT) CODA-CERVA (BE) NCIPD (BG) SUJCHBO (CZ) RKI (DE) BwIM (DE) FLI (DE) UMR (DE)	BNITM (DE) DTU (DK) TA (EE) BIOEF (ES) ISCIH (ES) THL (FI) INSERM (FR) DGA (FR)	AUT (GR) HZJZ (HR) NCE (HU) INMI (IT) ISS (IT) IZSLER (IT) NVSPL (LT) RIVM (NL)	ERASMUS MC (NL) NIPH (NO) NVI (NO) NIPH-NIH (PL) NVRI (PL) INSA (PT) INC (RO) FoHM (SE) PHE (UK)
Objectives	<p>EMERGE aims to ensure efficient response to serious emergent and re-emergent cross-border events by reinforcing the existing EU network of BSL-3 and BSL-4 laboratories which are already active in the field of identification of dangerous bacterial and viral human pathogens. The JA contributes to provide an integrated European laboratory infrastructure and strategy to protect European citizens against exposure to a panel of globally recognized high threat bacteria and viruses.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Networking of networks for laboratory response establishing and strengthening the cooperation between networks. - Improving capabilities for rapid laboratory diagnosis of new or emerging pathogens (e.g. sample sharing) - Quality Assurance for laboratory diagnostics by External Quality Assurance Exercises (EQAE). - Training on diagnostics and biorisk management. - All activities are planned for a direct laboratory response in relevant outbreak situations and for improvement of laboratory preparedness in interepidemic phases. 			
Work Packages	WP1. Coordination of the Joint Action. WP2. Dissemination of the Joint Action activities. WP3. Evaluation of the Joint Action. WP4. Networking of networks for laboratory response. WP5. Rapid capabilities for diagnoses. WP6. Quality assurance of laboratory Diagnostics.			

	WP7. Training on diagnostics and biorisk management.
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^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	A novel cross-sectorial platform for the integration of genomics in surveillance of foodborne pathogens			
Acronym	INNUENDO			
Website	http://www.innuendoweb.org/			
Coordinator's name	Mirko Rossi			
Contact details	mirko.rossi@helsinki.fi			
Coordinator's Institution	University of Helsinki (UH), Finland			
Funding programme	European Food and Safety Agency (EFSA) Grant agreement GP/EFSA/AFSCO/2015/01/CT2			
Duration	2016.01.15 – 2018.07.15			
Total budget				
Consortium^a	8 partners, 6 countries			
	VFL (EE) UPV/EHU (ES)	Vetmeduni Viena (AT) UH (FI)	THL (FI) BIOR (LV)	ULisboa (PT) IANPHI (PT)
Objectives	<p>The overall objective of our proposal is to deliver a standardized, cross-sectorial framework for integration of bacterial whole genome sequencing in routine surveillance and epidemiological investigations to reduce the burden of disease caused by both epidemic and sporadic food-borne zoonotic infections.</p> <p>The specific objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to identify the functionalities and flaws in sharing data related to national and transnational outbreak investigations caused by foodborne pathogens. - to calibrate the genetic diversity of foodborne pathogen populations using an evolutionary framework to assess the epidemiological relationship among bacterial isolates in the food chain. - to design an IT infrastructure and develop bioinformatics solutions for storage, mirroring, sharing and analysis of whole genome sequencing data for use in tracking foodborne pathogens. - to develop a reactive standard framework for assessing the effectiveness of whole genome sequencing in outbreaks and surveillance, and evaluate the possibilities of efficient utilization of whole genome sequencing based information in solving the outbreaks. 			
Work Packages	<p>WP1. Data flow calibration: data collection and sequencing & metadata and data flow assessment.</p> <p>WP2. Phylogenetic calibration: <i>Campylobacter</i> and <i>Yersinia</i> & <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Salmonella</i>.</p> <p>WP3. Infrastructure development: QA/QC methodologies and Network development & Fast Clustering speciation and typing (FCST) & Species-specific gene-by-gene framework.</p> <p>WP4. Proof-of-concept actions: national outbreak investigations & simulation multinational outbreak.</p>			

^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	European Joint Action on antimicrobial resistance and associated interactions			
Acronym	JAMRAI			
Website	https://eu-jamrai.eu/			
Coordinator's name	Marie Cecile Ploy			
Contact details	Marie-cecile.ploy@unilim.fr			
Coordinator's Institution	French National Institute of Health and Medical Research (INSERM), France			
Funding programme	European Union Grant Agreement 761296			
Duration	2017.09.01 – 2020.08.31			
Total budget	4,178,162.75 euros			
Consortium^a	44 partners; 22 countries			
	GOG (AT) FPS HFCSE (BE) NCIPD (BG) NIPH (CZ) RKI (DE) SSI (DK) TA (EE) AEMPS (ES) GENCAT (ES) CSGIB (ES) DGPIFAC/FFIS/SMS (ES)	FMS (ES) SAS/FISEVI/IBIS (ES) ISCIII (ES) SERMAS (ES) ANSES (FR) INSERM (FR) MoH (FR) HCDCP (GR) ESDY-NSPH (GR) 7HRC (GR) CIPH (HR)	UNIFG (IT) ISS (IT) LSMULKK (LT) VULSK (LT) HI (LT) NVSC (LT) PSKUS (LV) VWS (NL) HdiR (NO) FHI (NO) NVI (NO)	NMI (PL) DGS (PT) UMPIH (RO) FOHM (SE) SOS (SE) SBA (SE) NFA (SE) SVA (SE) SRC (SE) UAS (SE) NIJZ (SI)
Objectives	<p>The overarching objective of EU-JAMRAI is to support European Union Member States, develop and implement effective One Health policies to combat Antimicrobial Resistance and reduce Healthcare-Associated Infections. Through appropriate involvement of each group in the different planned actions, the Joint Action will strengthen existing public health policies both at national and European level and contribute to achieving the objectives of the WHO Global Action Plan on AMR, the Council Conclusions on AMR and the EU Action Plan on AMR.</p> <p>General Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To identify and test evidence-based measures to address AMR and HCAI in different contexts and provide recommendations to policymakers. - To bring together different networks of policymakers, experts and organisations working on AMR and HCAI. - To promote: The One Health approach; One Health in all policies concept; and Health in all policies concept. - To produce concrete recommendations and promote awareness and commitment by governments and stakeholders for a European contribution to international initiatives. 			
Work Packages	WP1. Management. WP2. Dissemination.			

	<p>WP3. Evaluation.</p> <p>WP4. Integration in National Policies and sustainability.</p> <p>WP5. Implementation of One Health national strategies and National Action Plans for AMR.</p> <p>WP6. Policies for prevention of HCAI and their implementation.</p> <p>WP7. Appropriate use of antimicrobials in human and in animals.</p> <p>WP8. Awareness raising and communication.</p> <p>WP9. Prioritizing and implementing research and innovation for public health needs.</p>
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^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance (JPIAMR)			
Acronym	JPIAMR			
Website	www.jpiamr.eu			
Coordinator's name	Mats Ulfendahl			
Contact details	secretariat.jpiamr@vr.se ; mats.ulfendahl@ki.se			
Coordinator's Institution	Swedish Research Council in Stockholm (Sweden)			
Funding programme	European Union			
Duration	Ongoing from 2011			
Total budget	65 M Euros			
Consortium^a	27 countries			
	Argentina Belgium Canada Czech Republic Denmark Egypt United Kingdom	Estonia Finland France Germany Greece Ireland Israel	Italy India Japan The Netherlands Norway Poland	Romania South Africa Spain Sweden Switzerland Turkey
Objectives	<p>The mission for JPIAMR is to join forces across nations by leading the alignment, coordination, and support to Antimicrobial Resistance One Health collaborative research and global policy activities".</p> <p>The overarching major goals are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To align national and international research programmes. - To support and coordinate transformative research. - To support and coordinate the JPIAMR Virtual Research Institute. - To promote innovation and translation of research results. - To bridge the gap between research and policy. 			
Work Packages	<p>Priority topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - THERAPEUTICS: Development of novel antibiotics and alternatives for antibiotics – from basic research to the market. - DIAGNOSTICS: Design strategies to improve treatment and prevention of infections by developing new diagnostics. - SURVEILLANCE: Implementation of a publicly funded global antibiotic resistance surveillance program. - TRANSMISSION: Transmission dynamics. - ENVIRONMENT: The role of the environment and sewage as a source for the emergence and spread of antimicrobial resistance. <p>INTERVENTIONS: Designing and testing interventions to prevent acquisition, transmission and infection caused by antibiotic-resistant bacteria.</p>			

^a OHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Veterinary Biocontained facility Network for excellence in animal infectious disease research and experimentation				
Acronym	VetBioNet				
Website	http://www.vetbionet.eu/				
Coordinator's name	Frederic Lantier				
Contact details	frederic.lantier@inra.fr				
Coordinator's Institution	Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique (INRA), France				
Funding programme	European Union's Horizon 2020 Grant agreement 731014				
Duration	2017.03.01 – 2022.02.28				
Total budget	10,017,890.50 euros				
Consortium^a	27 partners, 14 countries				
	AAHL (AUS) EDI-IVI (CH) FLI (DE) ISX (DE) LEICA (DE) AU (DK) INIA (ES)	IRTA (ES) INGENASA (ES) INRA (FR) ANSES (FR) NUID-UCD (IE) IZSve (IT) EAAP (IT)	ILRI (KEN) WBVR (NL) Erasmus MC (NL) Noldus (NL) PIWET (PL) TPI (UK) APHA (UK)	MRI (UK) MS (UK) UEDIN (UK) UNOTT (UK) EpiBio (UK) VAL (UK)	
Objectives	<p>VetBioNet seeks to complement and strengthen the present European capacity and competence to meet the challenges of (re)emerging infectious diseases by establishing a comprehensive network of pre-eminent European high-containment (BSL3) infrastructures, international organisations, and industry partners that is dedicated to advance research on epizootic and zoonotic diseases and to promote technological developments.</p> <p>To reach this overall objective VetBioNet will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote and facilitate Transnational Access (TNA) to the infrastructure resources of the network, including BSL3 animal experimental facilities and laboratories, technological platforms, and sample collections. - Promote technological development by involving private partners in the integrating activities of the network and by providing a communication platform for bidirectional exchange with industry stakeholders (Stakeholder Platform). - Enhance the preparedness of the major European BSL3 research infrastructures to accelerate the response to (re)emerging epizootic and zoonotic threats by sharing capacities beyond the infrastructures. - Harmonise Best Practices and promote the use of global standards in European BSL3 infrastructures. - Forge cooperative relationships with non-European BSL3 infrastructures, research institutes, industrial partners, international organisations, and policy makers. - Ensure high ethical standards and clarify the social impact of VetBioNet research work. 				

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop and implement a Sustainability Plan for the network to continue beyond the five-year term of funding. - Carry out Joint Research Activities (JRAs) designed to improve the scientific and technological standards of the integrated services provided by the network infrastructures.
<p>Work Packages</p>	<p>WPs 1-6. Networking Activities: WP1. Transnational Access Management; WP2. Development of a Preparedness Plan to enhance the preparedness of the VetBioNet BSL3 research infrastructures to respond to emerging infectious disease threats; WP3. Harmonisation of Best Practices and Biosafety/security standards; WP4. Ethical standards and social impact of VetBioNet research work; WP5. Dissemination, Data Management, and Training opportunities; WP6. Development and implementation of a Sustainability Plan.</p> <p>WPs 7-9. Joint Research Activities: WP7. Establishing novel and/or optimised infection models; WP8. Developing and/or validating novel analytical tools; WP9. Developing and/or validating novel telemetric or imaging tools.</p> <p>WP10. Project Management.</p> <p>WPs 11-31. Transnational Access Activities: to provide direct access to the partners' proprietary BSL3 infrastructures and technological platforms as well as remote access to the partners' sample collections, cell lines, immunological reagents, and animals</p>

^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Global Microbial Identifier	
Acronym	GMI	
Website	http://www.globalmicrobialidentifier.org/	
Coordinator's name	Frank Aarestrup	
Contact details	fmaa@food.dtu.dk	
Coordinator's Institution	Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Denmark	
Funding programme	In-kind	
Duration	On going from 2011	
Total budget	In-kind	
Consortium^a	260 experts from 50 countries	
Objectives	<p>GMI envisions a global system of DNA genome databases for microbial and infectious disease identification and diagnostics. Such a system will benefit those tackling individual problems at the frontline, clinicians, veterinarian, etc., as well as policy-makers, regulators, and industry. By enabling access to this global resource, a professional response on health threats will be within reach of all countries with basic laboratory infrastructure.</p> <p>A global system to aggregate, share, mine and translate genomic data for microorganisms in real-time is a realistic goal. A system enabling a direct link from end-users in academia, industry and government (e.g. clinicians, veterinarians, epidemiologist, microbiologists) to main databases through user-friendly platforms would provide significant societal advantages, including a safe and nutritious food supply. This system could include a reference database which could be accessed both for single clinical tasks (simple microbiological identification) as well as for national and international public health surveillance and outbreak investigation and response.</p>	
Work Groups	<p>WG1. Political challenges, outreach and building a global network. WG1 is developing a long-term plan to shape political level involvement in GMI development at the global, regional and national level.</p> <p>WG2. Repository and storage of sequence and meta-data. WG2 strives towards developing a format to capture "Minimum Data for Matching (MDM)", consisting of reads and minimum metadata.</p> <p>WG3. Analytical approaches. WG3 is providing guidance for the development of analytical tools for optimal positioning and functioning of the GMI platform.</p> <p>WG4. Ring trials and quality assurance. WG4 is aiming for all laboratories globally to conduct NGS on bacteria and virus to the highest degree of quality.</p>	

^a OHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

APPENDIX M: Topic description form

TOPIC DESCRIPTION FORM

Old topic title: _____

New title	<p><i>Please generate an informative title, specifying:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>the methods and data types of the research carried out in this topic;</i> • <i>the pathogens or groups of pathogens that will be the focus of this topic;</i> • <i>the populations that will be target of the research carried out in this topic</i>
Context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Please shortly provide the rationale and relevance of the research conducted in this topic.</i> • <i>Please specify possible strategic interactions (or overlaps) with other EU projects/initiatives.</i> • <i>Please also specify which stakeholders' needs, national priorities, and gaps in the current work plan are addressed by the topic.</i>
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Please specify what the research activities of this topic are intended to attain or accomplish, including purposes, goals and targets.</i> • <i>Please specify the methods, data types, pathogens or groups of pathogens, and populations that will be target of the research carried out in this topic.</i> • <i>Please specify whether either the human, animal or environment dimensions are to be targeted.</i>
Expected results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Please specify what desired data, knowledge, tools, systems, etc. should be obtained by the research conducted in this topic. Providing a few examples is encouraged.</i> • <i>Please specify the potential short- and long-term impact of the research within this topic.</i>

APPENDIX N: List of European stakeholders' needs

GENERAL INFORMATION

This document contains a schematic summary of research needs expressed by different European stakeholders (EFSA, ECDC and DG SANTE) so that it can be counted how many times a given need has been expressed by the three stakeholders. The experts are asked to check this summary when assessing the criterion number 4 of the MCDA for the prioritization of the narrowed down research topics.

Research need	ECDC	EFSA	DG SANTE
Rapid risk assessment tools for introduction of zoonotic and foodborne diseases.		X	
Development of new tools for early (real-time) detection of resistant pathogens in humans and animals, as well as new diagnostic tools in particular on-site tests for humans and animals.		X	X
Understanding AMR pathways of transmission between animals and humans, and their impact.		X	X
Development of new tools for monitoring antimicrobials and microorganisms resistant against antimicrobials in the environment.		X	X
Strengthened infection prevention and control measures, development of new effective preventive vaccines, development and assessment of interventions that prevent the development and spread of AMR.		X	X
Development of new economic models, exploring and analysing incentives to boost the development of new therapeutics, alternatives, vaccines and diagnostics.		X	X
Development of technologies that enable efficient and rapid degradation of antimicrobials in wastewater and the environment and reduce the spread of AMR		X	X
Improving knowledge on the release of resistant microorganisms and antimicrobials into the environment and their (environment-mediated) spread. Assessing the role of the environment in AMR transmission, taking into account that animals are not the only source of contamination of the environment with antimicrobials and antimicrobial-resistant microorganisms. Explore risk assessment methodologies to evaluate the risks to human and animal health from the presence of antimicrobials in the environment.	X	X	X
Better tools for foodborne outbreak detection and investigation.	X	X	
Development of efficient and optimised cell culture methods for HEV (reproducibility and sensitivity). Level of HEV contamination in foods of animal origin (e.g. foods other than pig liver products). Correlation of HEV RNA detection with infectivity of the virus. Impact of vaccination and management methods of pig herds against HEV and other options, such as HEV-free pig herds. Survival of HEV in meat products, bivalve molluscs, fruit and vegetables and their production and processing environment are needed. Risk of transmission of HEV from contaminated water to food.	X	X	
Assessing the high economic impact as well as the impact of frequent identification of clusters through application of whole genome sequencing for foodborne outbreak detection.		X	X
Implementing network science and mathematical modelling tools into EU food safety decision making.		X	
Source attribution studies indicating the role of the environment and of other reservoirs (e.g. pets) as sources of zoonoses, zoonotic agents and antimicrobial resistance.		X	
<i>Salmonella</i> control beyond poultry, especially in pigs.		X	X
Reasons as to why the decreasing trend of <i>Salmonella</i> seems to have stopped.	X	X	
Better detection and investigation of outbreaks of antimicrobial-resistant pathogens linked to food animals.	X	X	
Improving data generation and collection, sequencing, prevalence and concentration of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> in RTE foods and human cases.	X	X	

Improving data generation and collection, and sequencing for Shiga toxin-producing <i>Escherichia coli</i> (STEC) infections in humans and occurrence/prevalence in foods and animals, also addressing the global epidemiology and the fact that more and more hybrid STEC strains continue to emerge.	X	X	
Cross-sectorial investigations to understand the underlying reasons (e.g. premature relaxation of the effective control measures, less farm hygiene controls to reduce costs) for the increase in <i>S. Enteritidis</i> outbreaks and trends from surveillance data, as they indicate a reversal of the decreasing trend in the EU in humans and poultry. To conduct research into possible discrepancies between <i>Salmonella</i> sampling and testing schemes (from food and animals) from competent authorities versus food business operators.	X	X	X
Intervention studies to determine the effectiveness of preventing exposure to risk factors for <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> infection.		X	
One Health-oriented research on the epidemiology of food-borne yersiniosis, taking into account biotype and also serotype information of strains involved in human yersiniosis cases, food-borne outbreaks and food-animal isolates.	X	X	
Trade patterns: risk mapping approach.	X		
Using "Big Data" gathered in food production to be used for food safety/quality risk assessment.		X	
Investigations on the emergence of resistant strains originating from the food chain.		X	X
The impact of the sensitivity of the statutory sampling implemented in commercial laying hen flocks with low within-flock prevalence on the identification of positive flocks and the risk of under-detection of positive flocks especially in major exporting MS and the possible increased spread of <i>Salmonella</i> needs to be assessed.		X	X

APPENDIX O: Subdivision of the experts between subgroups within domains

DOMAIN	SUBGROUP	Uni_GROUP	Expert	Institute	Country	Theme expertise	Vet/Med	Facilitator	COLOR			
Foodborne zoonoses	1	FBZ-1	Henrik Vedel Nielsen	SSI	DK	AM	Med	Free role	Red	Free role	Reserve	
			Karsten Nöckler	BfR	DE	HMI	Vet					
			Solveig Jore	FHI	NO	EPI	Med					
			Francesco Pomilio	IZSAM	IT	INT	Vet					
	2	FBZ-2	Sabine Schlager	AGES	AT	AM	Med	Annemarie				
				IISPV	RO	HMI	Vet					
	2	FBZ-2	Laurentiu Mihai Ciupescu	Piwet	PL	EPI	Vet					
				Dariusz Wasyl	PL	EPI	Vet					
	2	FBZ-2	Renata Karpšková	VRI	CZ	RA	Vet					
				INIAV	PT	AM	Vet	Hein				
	3	FBZ-3	Ana Botelho	NDRVMI	BG	HMI	Vet					
				Gergana Krumova-Valcheva	BG	HMI	Vet					
	3	FBZ-3	Mirko Faber	RKI	DE	EPI	Med					
				NVI	NO	INT	Vet					
	3	FBZ-3	Merete Hofshagen	DTU	DK	RA	Vet					
				Maarten Nauta	DK	RA	Vet					
Antimicrobial resistance	1	AMR-1	Dik Mevius	WBVR	NL	AM	Vet	Luca	Yellow			
Antimicrobial resistance	1	AMR-1	Bruno González-Zom	VISA VET-UCM	ES	HMI	Vet		Yellow			
Antimicrobial resistance	1	AMR-1	Philippe Glaser	IP	FR	EPI	Med		Yellow			
Antimicrobial resistance	1	AMR-1	Jakob Ottoson	SLV	SE	RA	Vet		Yellow			
Antimicrobial resistance	2	AMR-2	Sara Byfors	FoHM	SE	AM	Med	Lucia	Yellow			
Antimicrobial resistance	2	AMR-2	Triin Tedersoo	VFL	EE	HMI	Vet		Yellow			
Antimicrobial resistance	2	AMR-2	Chris Teale	APHA	UK	EPI	Vet		Yellow			
Antimicrobial resistance	2	AMR-2	Kieran Jordan	TEAGASC	IE	INT	Vet		Yellow			
Antimicrobial resistance	2	AMR-2	Veljo Kisand	UTARTU	EE	RA	Med		Yellow			
Antimicrobial resistance	3	AMR-3	Jean-Yves Midec	ANSES	FR	AM	Vet	Free role	Yellow			
Antimicrobial resistance	3	AMR-3	Louise O'Connor	NUIG	IE	HMI	Med		Yellow			
Antimicrobial resistance	3	AMR-3	Stefan Börjesson	SVA	SE	EPI	Vet		Yellow			
Antimicrobial resistance	3	AMR-3	Giovanni Alborali	IZSLER	IT	INT	Vet		Yellow			
Emerging threats	1	ET-1	Kis Zoltan	NCE	HU	AM	Vet	Roberto	Blue			
			Philippe Velge	INRA	FR	HMI	Vet					
			Rita Sousa	INSA	PT	EPI	Med					
	2	ET-2	Stefano Morabito	ISS	IT	AM	Med	Ann		Blue		
				INIA	ES	HMI	Vet			Blue		
	2	ET-2	Miguel Angel Jiménez	RIVM	NL	EPI	Med			Blue		
				PHE	UK	INT	Med			Blue		
	3	ET-3	Steven Van Gucht	Sciensano	BE	HMI	Med	Free role		Blue		
				FLI	DE	EPI	Vet			Blue		
	3	ET-3	Herbert Tomaso	NIPH	CZ	RA	Med			Blue		
				Dan Horton	Surrey	UK	INT	Vet			Blue	

APPENDIX P: List of integrative topics to be prioritized

Overview of the integrative topics

Topic code	Topic title	Selected in first round	Included in prioritization
IA-1	Common frameworks for design and methods to assess equivalence between surveillance and control activities	No	Yes
IA-2	Harmonized protocols and common best practice	No	Yes
IA-3	Joint databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata	No	Yes
IA-4	Interpretation of surveillance data - Standardized data formats and ontologies, common tools and procedures for data analyses, including interpretation of sequence data.	Yes	No
IA-5	Common reporting and signaling procedures, joint platform for sharing surveillance data and their interpretation, incl. risk assessments	Yes	No
IA-6	Mentoring (twinning) system for sharing of best intervention practice	No	Yes
IA-7	Aligned use of experimental facilities and models (of transmission, ecology, risk assessment etc.)	No	Yes

Integrative topic 1: Common frameworks for design and methods to assess equivalence between surveillance and control activities

Context

- Surveillance activities vary in nature between the Med-Vet sectors, where the former is usually passive in nature whereas the latter often involves active surveillance activities. There is no joint framework for the integrated design and evaluation of cost-efficient surveillance along the food chain and across the Med-Vet interface.
- Such a framework would provide the necessary guidance and ensure that surveillance, incl. official controls, is more transparent, comparable, cost-efficient and meets societal needs.
- Certain animal health surveillance objectives (case finding, prevalence estimation, early detection) show many similarities with the objectives of official controls in the food chain, for example in the application of risk-based approaches. However, whereas the former has increasingly moved towards output-based standards, such standards are still lacking for many areas of official controls, or are not being applied.

Objectives

- To conduct an inventory of existing frameworks for design and evaluation of surveillance, incl. official controls
 - To complement and adapt such frameworks for surveillance of food-borne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats across the Med-Vet sectors
 - To apply the frameworks in selected partner countries, for prioritised hazards in all domains.
 - To evaluate drivers and constraints to adoption of the frameworks and adapt them accordingly.
- To apply frameworks for assessing equivalence between national control programmes, incl. programmes that are part of official controls, for prioritized hazards in all domains.

Expected results

- Existing frameworks for design and evaluation of cost-efficient surveillance are adapted for use across the Med-Vet sectors
- At least four inter-sectoral surveillance activities for prioritised hazards have been designed or redesigned using the frameworks, leading to increased cost-effectiveness.
- The frameworks are regularly applied in at least four MS and forms an integral part of the surveillance policy cycle, leading to higher quality surveillance output and better official controls at the EU level.

Integrative topic 2: Harmonized protocols and common best practice

Context

- For all relevant hazards in the chain from feed to food, European Union Reference Laboratories (EURLs) are established. Their function is to ensure MS have the national capacity to carry out relevant laboratory investigations for the hazards in question. No such structure exists on the public health side, and some pathogens of relevance do not have an EURL.
- There is a rapid transition to NGS methods for typing of foodborne pathogens, and for characterising resistance mechanisms.
- In order to increase the usefulness of NGS and non-NGS data nationally and internationally, there is a need for harmonisation by agreement on common strategies and protocols.

Objectives

- To conduct a needs assessment for identification of methodological fields in prioritised need of harmonisation across the Med-Vet interface.
- Based on the needs assessment, develop harmonised protocols for detection and typing of foodborne pathogens and AMR determinants.
- Implement harmonised protocols for detection and typing of foodborne pathogens and AMR determinants.

Expected results

- An action plan describing the state of the art with regard to harmonisation of laboratory methods across Europe, including a list of prioritised fields.
- Harmonised protocols for detection and typing of prioritised foodborne pathogens and AMR determinants are developed and implemented in all partner institutes.
- Mechanisms for ensuring prospective harmonisation in the implementation of new methods for detection and typing of foodborne pathogens and AMR determinants.

Integrative topic 3: Joint databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata

Context

- Databases of reference materials as well as sequence databases exist nationally and in some cases also at the EU level.
- Such data are poorly accessible across the MedVet sectors, often due to issues with data sharing.
- Well defined reference materials or reference data are necessary for test development, for use in proficiency testing or for use in the tracing of outbreaks. These include strain collections as well as sequence collection of genomes, virulence, resistance genes and mobile genetic elements.

Objectives

- To conduct an inventory of national strain collections and associated sequence databases, for hazards in all domains.
- To define procedures for alignment and sharing of sequence data.
- To complement existing platform for storage of and access to sequence data, for hazards in all domains

Expected results

- An EU-wide overview of relevant national biological materials
- Common standards for recording of epidemiological data and metadata for biological materials
- Common standards for data sharing
- A joint platform for storage of and access to sequence data, for hazards in all domains

Context

- Approaches to the control of transmission of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats differ depending on biological, epidemiological, technical and socio-economic preconditions.
- The palette of control options available in the Med and Vet sectors, and geographically, also vary due to differences in policies, organizational structures and for financial reasons.
- As a result, the hazard situation varies across MS, and so does the national experiences with control of different pathogens at different stages along the food chain.

Objectives

- To carry out an inventory of the current practice with regard to interventions, for hazards in all domains.
- To facilitate transfer of experiences with interventions across MS by identifying context-specific best-practice.
- To build a mentoring/twinning network to allow active sharing of knowledge on best-practice interventions.

Expected results

- There is an overview of what interventions are in place across the Med-Vet sectors to prevent transmission of prioritised hazards in all domains
- Context-specific best-practice has been identified and is shared among MS by means of twinning activities.

Integrative topic 7: Aligned use of experimental facilities and models (of transmission, ecology, risk assessment etc.)

Context

- An FP7-funded project for organizing European animal infectiology centers to achieve economies of scale and modernize existing facilities (NADIR) was concluded in 2013, with many but not all EJP partners.
- Computer models are widely used to understand biological processes that subsequently inform approaches to prevention and control. The development of generic and/or common modeling frameworks can enhance transparency, communication and usefulness of model output in informing national and EU policies.
- Data abundance allows for the development of data-driven modeling approaches; however, computational capacity is becoming a bottleneck which calls for more efficient code and algorithms.

Objectives

- To integrate additional EJP partners into the Network of Animal Disease Infectiology Research Facilities (NADIR).
- To conduct an inventory of modelling frameworks available within partner institutes, that are used to inform surveillance and control activities and for conducting risk assessments.
- To identify or develop modelling frameworks that meet prioritised needs of all EJP domains.
- To make such modelling frameworks available for research and routine work via a relevant platform format.

Expected results

- An active EU wide network of BSL-3 facilities for studies of animal infectious diseases.
- An action plan describing the state of the art with regard to availability of models of relevance to the EJP across Europe, including a list of prioritised fields for development.
- A joint platform where modelling frameworks for the design of surveillance and control activities, as well as for risk assessments, can be accessed and maintained.

APPENDIX Q: European stakeholders' needs for integrative activities

Research need	ECDC	EFSA	DG SANTE
Supporting the mapping of actors, developing guidelines/best practices, investigating tools (e.g. ECDC toolkit), trainings/simulation exercises, strengthening the engagement of stakeholders to share data.	X		
Filling data gaps for source attribution models for zoonoses and zoonotic agents and epidemiological investigations, namely: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Collecting typing data in a standardized fashion from epidemiologically representative collections of isolates of <i>Salmonella</i>, <i>Campylobacter</i>, <i>L. monocytogenes</i> and <i>Y. enterocolitica</i>, with biotype and serotyping data, from a broad range of sources (e.g. food, humans and food-producing animals). Conducting investigation at the molecular level to identify, e.g., isolates with similar characteristics in foods, humans and food-producing animals. Applying source attribution models for other pathogens, including research and evaluation of the use of results for supporting risk management decision making. 		X	
To improve knowledge on animal populations (including wildlife) and their distribution across the EU, as well as their trade/movement patterns. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Establishing 'denominators' of populations: animal and human population distribution, structure and movements. Animal data should include domestic, farmed and wild free-ranging animals. Investigating analytical techniques for population surveys related to complex sampling designs. 		X	
Better data on food consumption for detailed food categories, possibly also feed consumption.		X	
Mechanisms for accessibility, transparency, and updating of data.		X	
Strengthened One Health surveillance and reporting of AMR and antimicrobial use.			X
Investigations on foods of animal origin (e.g. foods other than those containing pig liver) to collect data on the occurrence of the hepatitis E virus, e.g. prevalence, distribution, etc.		X	
To develop methods and formats for systematic data collection of multi-country foodborne outbreaks including integrated parameters/indicators for human and non-human data.	X		

APPENDIX R: Outcome of partner consultation regarding needs for integrative projects

GENERAL INFORMATION

This document contains a schematic summary of integrative needs expressed by partner countries so that it can be seen how many times a given need has been expressed by the OHEJP partners. This is needed to assess **ITC1: Number of needs expressed by One Health EJP partners that are addressed**. To assess this criterion, the information on needs already covered by the ongoing projects (ORION, COHESIVE) should also be taken into account (see Appendix).

It also contains schematic summaries of information needed to assess **ITC3: Recurrence of the issue addressed by the integrative activity across domains**, and **ITC4: Integration along the axis of the 'prevention, detection and response'-chain**.

ITC1: Number of needs expressed by One Health EJP partners that are addressed

In summary, a total of **36 integrative needs** were suggested in the second consultation. These were further categorised by the country respondents themselves into one or more of the following **seven types of integrative activities**:

ITC3: Recurrence of the issue addressed by the integrative activity across domains

The **seven types of integrative activities** were subsequently correlated with the **EJP domains** (one or more), as follows:

Integrative activities		Domains		
		Foodborne zoonoses	Antimicrobial resistance	Emerging threats
IA1	capacity building/training	12	10	12
IA2	experimental facilities	2	2	2
IA3	detection-/typing methods/protocols/GLP	12	9	13
IA4	strain collections/reference materials/bio-banks	8	7	9
IA5	digital infrastructure/database/ data sharing protocols/ data access/bioinformatics	21	18	23
IA6	surveillance strategies/reporting/signalling	10	8	12
IA7	legal/policy aspects	6	4	5

ITC4: Integration along the axis of the ‘prevention, detection and response’-chain

Furthermore, the **seven types of integrative activities** were also correlated with the EJP themes (note that each need can be related to one or more themes), as follows:

Integrative activities		Themes				
		Analytical methods	Host-microbe interaction	Risk assessment	Epidemiology	Intervention
IA1	capacity building/training	7	2	9	8	4
IA2	experimental facilities	1	2	1	0	0
IA3	detection-/typing methods/protocols/GLP	12	1	5	7	4
IA4	strain collections/reference materials/bio-banks	8	7	0	0	0
IA5	digital infrastructure/database/ data sharing protocols/ data access/bioinformatics	16	5	11	10	4
IA6	surveillance strategies/reporting/signalling	3	0	12	8	3
IA7	legal/policy aspects	1	0	5	3	3

[Appendix: List of integrative needs expressed by partner countries](#)

All needs expressed in the second consultation, grouped by type of integrative activity, are provided below. When a certain need was categorized into more than one integrative activity, it has been listed under all of them.

The tables also indicate whether the expressed needs are likely to be covered **by the integrative projects already funded in the first call** (COHESIVE, ORION).

Note that the actual call topics subsequently included in the 2nd call will build upon the needs expressed under each integrative activity below.

<p>focusing on a reasoned short list of bacteria, another on a reasoned short list of parasites etc.). This ensures that all pathogen groups are covered.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Includes inventory of current surveillance systems targeting the selected pathogens and including environment, as well as comparison and assessment of the different surveillance approaches and their effectiveness to detect new and emerging hazards and changing trends, by country and Med and Vet. • Includes capacity building and harmonizing • Includes development of tools needed for prioritization, identification of time and place for intervention, and decision-making support • Inclusion of partners of different current capacity levels is emphasized; partners can join for one or several of the focused work packages. <p>Produces specific, concrete recommendations for integrated Med-Vet approaches to the selected pathogens, and for including environment in these approaches.</p>	
<p>Sustainable and rapid systems for sharing reference materials, methods, tools, and data for One Health surveillance of zoonotic foodborne pathogens, antimicrobial resistance, and emerging threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing also reference materials, not only data, is needed for capacity building and harmonizing • Preparedness to share reference materials rapidly is needed for emerging threats • Includes harmonizing the nomenclature used • Helps in producing comparable results from different countries • Inclusion of partners of different current capacity levels is emphasized 	No
<p>Sustainable frameworks and systems for sharing tools, models and data for risk assessment and effective decision making</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing existing tools, models and data for “farm to fork” risk assessment and One Health decision support • Linkage with the EFSA Knowledge junction where possible • Development of standardised data formats and ontologies, common tools and procedures for data analyses • Development of the required software systems that allow the establishment of a framework for sustainable knowledge sharing, including the linkage and execution of risk assessment models • Establishment of a joint platform that facilitates rapid risk assessment, using all the data and knowledge available in the EU, as build up in the past, present and future • Training in the use of the framework • Helps in producing comparable results from different countries. • Inclusion of partners of different current capacity levels is emphasized. 	Yes (COHESIVE)
<p>Sustainable frameworks and systems for sharing tools, models and data for risk assessment and effective decision making</p>	Yes (COHESIVE)
<p>Establishment of a platform for sharing and analysing nucleotide sequences including whole genomes from food-borne zoonotic agents and emerging threats.</p>	Yes (COHESIVE)
<p>Development and harmonisation of NGS methods, including training and capacity building: sample preparation, sequencing and analysis, with emphasis on bioinformatics.</p>	No
<p>Risk communication taking into account cultural differences in food consumption habits</p>	No

One Health epi-lab network: joint databases, harmonized protocols and intervention practices to better prevent, detect, and respond to global infectious disease threats. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • implementation of WHO International Health Regulations, the OIE Veterinary Services Pathway, and other similar frameworks. • For achieving an adequate level of preparedness to tackle emerging health threats in animals and humans, an effective surveillance and communication between the human and animal counterparts is essential. 	Partly
Sharing best-practice approaches for early warning surveillance of (emerging) hazards	No
Strengthening the joint capacity to deal with a food-borne health crisis through arrangement of simulation exercises	No
Piloting blockchain technology for incorruptable exchange of surveillance information	No
Artificial intelligence (machine learning) for pathogen and AMR detection and tracking.	No

Integrative Activity 2: experimental facilities

Wordcloud from all the needs (2) referring to this integrative activity.

List of needs linked to this integrative activity, as suggested by the partners.

Integrative topic	Already covered
Innovative models of infection related to alternatives to in vivo experiments	No
Development and maintenance of EU-wide shared bio-banks and implementation of existing European registers	No

Integrative Activity 3: detection-/typing methods/protocols/GLP

Wordcloud from all the topics (14) referring to this integrative activity.

List of needs linked to this integrative activity, as suggested by the partners.

Integrative topic	Already covered
Development and Harmonisation of surveillance methods and protocols (e.g. for rapid detection) for selected emerging viruses" and reemerging viruses	No
Approaches to harmonize the typing methods and reporting procedure for pathogens isolated from human, zoonotic samples and food	No
Harmonisation of NGS sequencing and databanking strategy for comparison of human, animal and food-borne pathogens, and more particularly the practical exchange of molecular profiles between EU-RL and NRL (all directions), which would be very supportive in case of outbreaks (types of activity: capacity building; detection methods; digital infrastructure)	Partly
Provide a pipeline for bioinformatic analysis of the igome at the secretome and the genome level.	No
Alignment of phenotyping and genotyping (incl. NGS) data for the spread of food-borne pathogens with focus in risk characterization.	No
Sustainable and rapid systems for sharing reference materials, methods, tools, and data for One Health surveillance of zoonotic foodborne pathogens, antimicrobial resistance, and emerging threats	No

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing also reference materials, not only data, is needed for capacity building and harmonizing • Preparedness to share reference materials rapidly is needed for emerging threats • Includes harmonizing the nomenclature used • Helps in producing comparable results from different countries <p>Inclusion of partners of different current capacity levels is emphasized</p>	
Building the global capacity to develop WGS and metagenomics to assist with the detection, control and prevention of emerging and existing diseases including VTEC E. coli, Echinococcus and other zoonotic diseases together with the development of National strain collections and sequence database including standardised approaches for bioinformatic pipelines for use in official controls and global epidemiological investigations	No
Development and harmonisation of NGS methods, including training and capacity building: sample preparation, sequencing and analysis, with emphasis on bioinformatics.	No
Coordination of analytical methods	No
Development of best lab practice within the New Tech driven domains	No
<p>Identification and management of zoonotic threats associated with global changes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • promotion of intersectorial and multidisciplinary approaches to estimate and prevent global changes-related events as well as to prepare the authorities to put in place measures to reduce adverse human and animal health effects. 	No
<p>One Health epi-lab network: joint databases, harmonized protocols and intervention practices to better prevent, detect, and respond to global infectious disease threats.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • implementation of WHO International Health Regulations, the OIE Veterinary Services Pathway, and other similar frameworks. • For achieving an adequate level of preparedness to tackle emerging health threats in animals and humans, an effective surveillance and communication between the human and animal counterparts is essential. 	Partly
Strengthening the joint capacity to deal with a food-borne health crisis through arrangement of simulation exercises	No
Artificial intelligence (machine learning) for pathogen and AMR detection and tracking.	No

Integrative Activity 4: strain collections/reference materials/bio-banks

Wordcloud from all the needs (9) referring to this integrative activity.

List of needs linked to this integrative activity, as suggested by the partners.

Integrative topic	Already covered
Joint collections of reference materials and related data to be used for test development and in proficiency testing.	No
Inventory, alignment and sharing of national strain collections of infectious emerging threats and associated sequence databases (idem as in first call; types of activity: strain collections; digital infrastructure)	No
Capacity for development of current strain collection of zoonotic agents (bacteria cc a 2000 strains, viruses 500)	No
<p>Sustainable and rapid systems for sharing reference materials, methods, tools, and data for One Health surveillance of zoonotic foodborne pathogens, antimicrobial resistance, and emerging threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing also reference materials, not only data, is needed for capacity building and harmonizing • Preparedness to share reference materials rapidly is needed for emerging threats • Includes harmonizing the nomenclature used • Helps in producing comparable results from different countries <p>Inclusion of partners of different current capacity levels is emphasized</p>	No
Establish a strain collection and data base of the novel pathogens and a sequence collection of genomes, virulence, resistance genes and mobile genetic elements	No

Building the global capacity to develop WGS and metagenomics to assist with the detection, control and prevention of emerging and existing diseases including VTEC E. coli, Echinococcus and other zoonotic diseases together with the development of National strain collections and sequence database including standardised approaches for bioinformatic pipelines for use in official controls and global epidemiological investigations	No
Development and maintenance of EU-wide shared bio-banks and implementation of existing European registers	No
E-platform: Laboratory-based pathogen register	No
Inventory of national biological samples (strains, DNA, faeces, sera, etc.) collection of animal origin.	No

Alignment of phenotyping and genotyping (incl. NGS) data for the spread of food-borne pathogens with focus in risk characterization.	No
Sharing databases of NGS sequenced foodborne bacteria, viruses and parasites	Yes
<p>Sustainable and rapid systems for sharing reference materials, methods, tools, and data for One Health surveillance of zoonotic foodborne pathogens, antimicrobial resistance, and emerging threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing also reference materials, not only data, is needed for capacity building and harmonizing • Preparedness to share reference materials rapidly is needed for emerging threats • Includes harmonizing the nomenclature used • Helps in producing comparable results from different countries <p>Inclusion of partners of different current capacity levels is emphasized</p>	No
<p>Sustainable frameworks and systems for sharing tools, models and data for risk assessment and effective decision making</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing existing tools, models and data for “farm to fork” risk assessment and One Health decision support • Linkage with the EFSA Knowledge junction where possible • Development of standardised data formats and ontologies, common tools and procedures for data analyses • Development of the required software systems that allow the establishment of a framework for sustainable knowledge sharing, including the linkage and execution of risk assessment models • Establishment of a joint platform that facilitates rapid risk assessment, using all the data and knowledge available in the EU, as build up in the past, present and future • Training in the use of the framework • Helps in producing comparable results from different countries. <p>Inclusion of partners of different current capacity levels is emphasized.</p>	Yes (COHESIVE)
Development of bio-informatic capacities and tools for the standardization and the analysis of large sequencing databases	No
Sustainable frameworks and systems for sharing tools, models and data for risk assessment and effective decision making	Yes (COHESIVE)
Linking human and animal surveillance to FBZ, emerging threats, antibiotic and biocide resistance through standardised descriptions, reporting and analysis; performance characteristics, challenges, legal and social implications of the surveillance systems; handling big data	Yes (ORION)
Establish a strain collection and data base of the novel pathogens and a sequence collection of genomes, virulence, resistance genes and mobile genetic elements	No
Building the global capacity to develop WGS and metagenomics to assist with the detection, control and prevention of emerging and existing diseases including VTEC E. coli, Echinococcus and other zoonotic diseases together with the development of National strain collections and sequence database including standardised approaches for bioinformatic pipelines for use in official controls and global epidemiological investigations	No

Development and maintenance of EU-wide shared bio-banks and implementation of existing European registers	No
Establishment of a digital infrastructure defining common standards for data sharing	Yes (ORION)
Establishment of a platform for sharing and analysing nucleotide sequences including whole genomes from food-borne zoonotic agents and emerging threats.	Yes (COHESIVE)
Development and harmonisation of NGS methods, including training and capacity building: sample preparation, sequencing and analysis, with emphasis on bioinformatics.	No
E-platform: Laboratory-based pathogen register	No
<p>Identification and management of zoonotic threats associated with global changes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • promotion of intersectorial and multidisciplinary approaches to estimate and prevent global changes-related events as well as to prepare the authorities to put in place measures to reduce adverse human and animal health effects. 	No
<p>One Health epi-lab network: joint databases, harmonized protocols and intervention practices to better prevent, detect, and respond to global infectious disease threats.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • implementation of WHO International Health Regulations, the OIE Veterinary Services Pathway, and other similar frameworks. • For achieving an adequate level of preparedness to tackle emerging health threats in animals and humans, an effective surveillance and communication between the human and animal counterparts is essential. 	Partly
<p>Med-Vet epidemic intelligence approach for surveillance and early detection of emerging threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The novel ECDC (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control) approach to Surveillance comprises tools that combine the use of several sources to detect public health threats. The process includes both Indicator based surveillance and event-based surveillance, and necessarily includes screening, filtering, validation, analysis and assessment. This approach fosters using unverified sources such as news or social media, by applying modern data science tools, strengthened by artificial intelligence. While this has been in practice for human health, the One Health field still has opportunities for improvement and therefore this remains a challenging and important topic for action 	Partly
Strengthening the joint capacity to deal with a food-borne health crisis through arrangement of simulation exercises	No
Piloting blockchain technology for incorruptable exchange of surveillance information	No
Artificial intelligence (machine learning) for pathogen and AMR detection and tracking.	No

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Includes capacity building and harmonizing • Includes development of tools needed for prioritization, identification of time and place for intervention, and decision-making support • Inclusion of partners of different current capacity levels is emphasized; partners can join for one or several of the focused work packages. <p>Produces specific, concrete recommendations for integrated Med-Vet approaches to the selected pathogens, and for including environment in these approaches.</p>	
Sustainable frameworks and systems for sharing tools, models and data for risk assessment and effective decision making	Yes (COHESIVE)
Linking human and animal surveillance to FBZ, emerging threats, antibiotic and biocide resistance through standardised descriptions, reporting and analysis; performance characteristics, challenges, legal and social implications of the surveillance systems; handling big data	Yes (ORION)
Integration of zoonotic pathogen data collection activities in human and animal populations	No
Building the global capacity to detect, control and prevent emerging diseases including the development of free access, easy to use decision support tools based on predictive modelling of pathogens to support various stakeholders	Yes (COHESIVE)
<p>Identification and management of zoonotic threats associated with global changes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • promotion of intersectorial and multidisciplinary approaches to estimate and prevent global changes-related events as well as to prepare the authorities to put in place measures to reduce adverse human and animal health effects. 	No
<p>Med-Vet epidemic intelligence approach for surveillance and early detection of emerging threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The novel ECDC (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control) approach to Surveillance comprises tools that combine the use of several sources to detect public health threats. The process includes both Indicator based surveillance and event-based surveillance, and necessarily includes screening, filtering, validation, analysis and assessment. This approach fosters using unverified sources such as news or social media, by applying modern data science tools, strengthened by artificial intelligence. While this has been in practice for human health, the One Health field still has opportunities for improvement and therefore this remains a challenging and important topic for action 	Partly
Sharing best-practice approaches for early warning surveillance of (emerging) hazards	No
Strengthening the joint capacity to deal with a food-borne health crisis through arrangement of simulation exercises	No
Piloting blockchain technology for incorruptable exchange of surveillance information	No
Artificial intelligence (machine learning) for pathogen and AMR detection and tracking.	No

Integrative Activity 7: legal/policy aspects

Wordcloud from all the needs (5) referring to this integrative activity.

List of needs linked to this integrative activity, as suggested by the partners.

Integrative topic	Already covered
Sustainable frameworks and systems for sharing tools, models and data for risk assessment and effective decision making	Yes (COHESIVE)
Linking human and animal surveillance to FBZ, emerging threats, antibiotic and biocide resistance through standardised descriptions, reporting and analysis; performance characteristics, challenges, legal and social implications of the surveillance systems; handling big data	Yes (ORION)
Risk communication taking into account cultural differences in food consumption habits	No
Identification and management of zoonotic threats associated with global changes. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • promotion of intersectorial and multidisciplinary approaches to estimate and prevent global changes-related events as well as to prepare the authorities to put in place measures to reduce adverse human and animal health effects. 	No
Sharing best-practice approaches for early warning surveillance of (emerging) hazards	No
Strengthening the joint capacity to deal with a food-borne health crisis through arrangement of simulation exercises	No

APPENDIX S: Other EU projects and initiatives, particularly platforms, repositories, databases and guidelines

GENERAL INFORMATION

This document contains information on other EU projects and initiatives, particularly platforms, repositories, databases and guidelines that link in some form to the mission of the integrative topics of OHEJP, to support the prioritization of the integrative topics by highlighting potential strategic interactions with the activities carried out within these topics. Information sheets with essential information (as well as secondary sources for further consultation) for all projects are contained in this document. The experts are asked to consider possible interactions with these projects/initiatives when prioritizing the integrative topics.

Foodborne zoonoses	Antimicrobial resistance	Emerging threats
<u>INNUENDO</u>	<u>JPIAMR</u>	<u>EMERGE</u>
<u>CORBEL</u>	<u>JAMRAI</u>	<u>EVAg</u>
<u>RAKIP</u>		<u>PREPARE</u>
<u>NEOH</u>		<u>VetBioNet</u>
<u>CWG-SCAR</u>		<u>enotice</u>
<u>STAR-IDAZ IRC</u>		<u>CORBEL</u>
<u>SIRCAH</u>		<u>NEOH</u>
		<u>CWG-SCAR</u>
		<u>STAR-IDAZ IRC</u>
		<u>SIRCAH</u>
		<u>EU CBRN CoE</u>

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP
Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	A novel cross-sectorial platform for the integration of genomics in surveillance of foodborne pathogens			
Acronym	INNUENDO			
Website	http://www.innuendoweb.org/			
Coordinator's name	Mirko Rossi			
Contact details	mirko.rossi@helsinki.fi			
Coordinator's Institution	University of Helsinki (UH), Finland			
Funding programme	European Food and Safety Agency (EFSA) Grant agreement GP/EFSA/AFSCO/2015/01/CT2			
Duration	2016.01.15 – 2018.07.15			
Total budget				
Consortium^a	8 partners, 6 countries			
	VFL (EE) UPV/EHU (ES)	Vetmeduni Viena (AT) UH (FI)	THL (FI) BIOR (LV)	ULisboa (PT) IANPHI (PT)
Objectives	<p>The overall objective of our proposal is to deliver a standardized, cross-sectorial framework for integration of bacterial whole genome sequencing in routine surveillance and epidemiological investigations to reduce the burden of disease caused by both epidemic and sporadic food-borne zoonotic infections.</p> <p>The specific objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to identify the functionalities and flaws in sharing data related to national and transnational outbreak investigations caused by foodborne pathogens. - to calibrate the genetic diversity of foodborne pathogen populations using an evolutionary framework to assess the epidemiological relationship among bacterial isolates in the food chain. - to design an IT infrastructure and develop bioinformatics solutions for storage, mirroring, sharing and analysis of whole genome sequencing data for use in tracking foodborne pathogens. - to develop a reactive standard framework for assessing the effectiveness of whole genome sequencing in outbreaks and surveillance, and evaluate the possibilities of efficient utilization of whole genome sequencing based information in solving the outbreaks. 			
Work Packages	<p>WP1. Data flow calibration: data collection and sequencing & metadata and data flow assessment.</p> <p>WP2. Phylogenetic calibration: <i>Campylobacter</i> and <i>Yersinia</i> & <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Salmonella</i>.</p> <p>WP3. Infrastructure development: QA/QC methodologies and Network development & Fast Clustering speciation and typing (FCST) & Species-specific gene-by-gene framework.</p> <p>WP4. Proof-of-concept actions: national outbreak investigations & simulation multinational outbreak.</p>			

^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP
Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science Services			
Acronym	CORBEL			
Website	http://www.corbel-project.eu/home.html			
Coordinator's name	Niklas Blomberg			
Contact details	niklas.blomberg@elixir-europe.org			
Coordinator's Institution	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Germany			
Funding programme	European Union's Horizon 2020 Grant agreement 654248			
Duration	2015.09.01 – 2019.08.31			
Total budget	14,837,800 euros			
Consortium^a	37 partners, 9 countries			
	BBMRI-ERIC (AT) MUW (AT) DKFZ (DE) DSMZ (DE) EMBL (DE) EMPHASIS (DE) FVB (DE) HMGU (DE) INFRAFRONTIER (DE)	JacobsUni (DE) MDC (DE) UDUS (DE) CRG (ES) CSIC (ES) ICFO (ES) CSI (FI) ECRIN (FR) ERINHA (FR)	CNRS (FR) BRFAA (GR) CIRMMP (IT) IRFMN (IT) SZN (IT) UNITO (IT) EATRIS (NL) Erasmus MC (NL) KNAW (NL)	UMCG (NL) UMCU (NL) VU/VUmc (NL) UNIVDUN (UK) UNIMAN (UK) CABI (UK) Imperial (UK) Instruct-ERIC (UK) U LIVERPOOL (UK) USTAN (UK)
Objectives	Create a platform for harmonised user access to biological and medical technologies, biological samples and data services required by cutting-edge biomedical Research. CORBEL will boost the efficiency, productivity and impact of European biomedical research.			
Work Packages	<p>WP1. Management and coordination.</p> <p>WP2. Documentation, communication and outreach.</p> <p>WP3. Community Driven Cross-Infrastructure joint research – Medical.</p> <p>WP4. Community Driven Cross-Infrastructure joint research – Bioscience.</p> <p>WP5. Enabling common solutions for user access.</p> <p>WP6. Data access, management and integration.</p> <p>WP7. Common services providing support with Ethical, Legal and Societal Issues.</p> <p>WP8. Accelerating innovation.</p> <p>WP9. Training.</p>			

^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP
Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Risk Assessment modelling and Knowledge Integration Platform Initiative			
Acronym	RAKIP			
Website	https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/rakip/			
Coordinator's name	Matthias Filter			
Contact details	Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR), Germany			
Coordinator's Institution	Matthias.Filter@bfr.bund.de			
Funding programme	ANSES, DTU, BfR			
Duration	Ongoing since 2017			
Total budget	In-kind funding of the three institutes (ANSES, DTU, BfR)			
Consortium^a	3 partners, 3 countries (from May 2018 it will become open for new partners)			
	BfR (DE)	DTU (DK)	ANSES (FR)	
Objectives	<p>The main objective is to establish new community resources facilitating the efficient knowledge integration and Exchange of data and models into and between IT-based applications and resources.</p> <p>The specific objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To create and maintain a knowledge exchange format. - To create and maintain a web-based food safety knowledge repository. - To develop new open source software libraries and converter tools. - To engage with the global food safety risk assessment community. 			
Work Packages	<p>Achievements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food Safety Knowledge Metadata schema. - Community driven Controlled Vocabularies for knowledge annotation. - Food Safety Knowledge Markup Language (FSK-ML). - Demonstrator RAKIP-Web-Portal: 1. RAKIP Model Repository; 2. Online Creation of Harmonized Models; 3. Upload of Harmonized Models. 			

^a OHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP
Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Network for Evaluation of One Health			
Acronym	NEOH			
Website	http://neoh.onehealthglobal.net/			
Coordinator's name	Barbara Häslar			
Contact details	bhaesler@rvc.ac.uk			
Coordinator's Institution	Royal Veterinary College (RVC), United Kingdom			
Funding programme	EU COST – European Cooperation in Science and Technology. EU H2020. <i>Action TD1404.</i>			
Duration	2014.11.17 – 2018.11.16			
Total budget	NA			
Consortium^a	39 partners, 24 countries			
	VFS-UNSA (BA) UGent (BE) ULG (BE) UZH (CH) SWUSSTPH (CH) NIV.NS.AC (CS) UNI-BONN (DE) H-BRS (DE) SUND (DK) UM (ES)	HTorrecardenas (ES) CIRAD (FR) AUTH (GR) VEF (HR) VEINST (HR) UNIVET (HU) DCU (IE) CIT (IE) HUJI-AC (IL) UNIBO (IT)	UNIMI (IT) InMedica (LT) FVM-UKIM (MK) ECCF-UKIM (MK) UM (MT) GOV (MT) WUR (NL) RIVM (NL) VETINST (NO) NMBU (NO)	INESCTEC (PT) UNL (PT) USAMCLUJ (RO) UBBCLUJ (RO) SVA (SE) UU (SE) UNI-LJ (SI) LIV (UK) SURREY (UK)
Objectives	<p>The overall aim of NEOH is to enable future quantitative evaluations of One Health activities and to further the evidence base by developing and applying a science-based evaluation protocol in a community of experts. NEOH will deliver:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A science-based evaluation protocol for One Health activities. - Coordination of evaluations of existing One Health initiatives. - A networked community of experts collaborating to further the evidence base. - Researchers trained in performing evaluations of One Health activities. 			
Work Packages	<p>The project is organised into four working groups (WG):</p> <p>WG1. Framework, protocol and index development: Conceptualisation, standardised framework, protocol and index for systematic evaluation of One Health.</p> <p>WG2. Framework application: Case studies based on application of framework, protocol and index to primary and secondary One Health datasets.</p> <p>WG3. Meta-analysis: Meta-analysis of case study results to facilitate international comparison and development of policy recommendations.</p> <p>WG4. Stakeholder engagement, dissemination and policy: Communication strategy, dissemination and best practice guidelines, Training School for key-stakeholders.</p>			

^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Collaborative Working Group on European Animal Health & Welfare Research (CWG), EU Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR)		European Animal Health & Welfare Research COLLABORATIVE WORKING GROUP	
Acronym	CWG-SCAR			
Website	http://www.scar-cwg-ahw.org/			
Coordinator's name	Marina Bagni			
Contact details	m.bagni@sanita.it			
Coordinator's Institution	Ministry of Health (MoH), Italy			
Funding programme	No budget, some actions funded by CASA (EC-CSA)			
Duration	Ongoing since 2005			
Total budget	NA			
Consortium^a	19 partners, 13 countries			
	FPS-CR (BE) MZE (CZ) FZJ-PTJ (DE) BMBF (DE) BLE (DE)	BMEL (DE) DFIA (DE) MMM (FI) INRA (FR) ELGO DEMETER, VRI (GR)	IVSAH (IL) MoH (IT) EZ (NL) NVWA (NL) RCN (NO)	Formas (SE) TAGEM (TR) DEFRA (UK) BBSRC (UK)
Objectives	<p>The main goal is to establish a durable and focused network of research funders from Member and Associated States of the EU – providing a forum leading to improved collaboration on research prioritisation and procurement, creating the necessary critical mass and focus to deliver the animal health and welfare research needs of our policy makers and the European livestock industry. The CWG objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share information on research projects. - Coordinate research activities. - Work towards a common research agenda. - Work towards mutual research funding activities, in the field of animal health, fish health and those conditions which pose a threat to human health. - Mapping the landscape in relation to provisions of Research facilities, including expertise and microorganism collection. 			
CWG activities	<p>The activities of the CWG were accelerated and built upon through the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - European Commission funded projects EMIDA (Coordination of European Research on Emerging and Major Infectious Diseases of Livestock, 2008 – 2011), - ANIHWA (Animal health and welfare – ERA-NET, 2012 – 2015), and - STAR-IDAZ (Global Strategic Alliances for the Coordination of Research on the Major Infectious Diseases of Animals and Zoonoses, 2011 – 2015). 			

^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP
Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	STAR-IDAZ International Research Consortium on Animal Health (IRC)			
Acronym	STAR-IDAZ IRC			
Website	http://www.star-idaz.net/			
Coordinator's name	Luke Dalton			
Contact details	Luke.Dalton@Defra.gsi.gov.uk			
Coordinator's Institution	DEFRA (UK)			
Funding programme	In-kind funding			
Duration	Ongoing since 2016			
Total budget	In-kind funding			
Consortium^a	25 partners, 16 countries			
	INTA (AR) MINCYT (AR) UGent/ULiege/FPS/ CODA-CERVA (BE) HealthforAnimals (BE) EC (BE) CFIA (CA)	DTU (DK) INIA (ES) INRA (FR) ANSES (FR) OIE (FR) Diagnostics for Animals (FR)	KVI (IL) MoH (IT) NIAH (JP) ILRI (KE) CONASA/UNAM/ FVMZ (MX) NAHRN (NI)	MinEZ (NL) TVLA (TZ) USDA-ARS (USA) Zoetis (USA) BMGF (USA) DEFRA (UK) BBSRC (UK)
Objectives	<p>The overall objective of STAR-IDAZ IRC is to coordinate research at international level to contribute to new and improved animal health strategies for at least 30 priority diseases/infections/issues.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthen the linkages between and reduce the duplication of global research effort on high priority infectious diseases of animals (including zoonoses) maximise the efficient use of expertise and resources and accelerate coordinated development of control methods. - Identify and co-ordinate the response to gaps in research activities for targeted diseases. - Create the necessary critical mass and capacity to address emerging infectious disease threats. - Improve the cost-effectiveness and added value to network partners of current research programmes. - Develop durable procedures for a better co-ordinated, rapid response to urgent research needs. - Identify unique regions with localised diseases and improve access to research in those areas. - Improve access to and the utility of research results across all partner organisations. 			
Work Packages	<p>Working Groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Immunology/vaccinology (tools and technologies) - Diagnostics (tools and technologies) - Innovative anti-infective approaches, including alternatives to anti-microbial agents - Influenza 			

STAR-IDAZ
International Research Consortium on Animal Health

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Bovine Tuberculosis- Foot and Mouth Disease- Brucellosis- African Swine Fever- Emerging issues- Vector-borne diseases- Coronaviruses- One Health (including food-borne pathogens and AMR)- Vector-borne Diseases
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^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP
Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Secretariat for the International Research Consortium on Animal Health		[Include logo]	
Acronym	SIRCAH			
Website				
Coordinator's name	Alex Morrow			
Contact details	Alex.Morrow@Defra.gsi.gov.uk			
Coordinator's Institution	Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA), United Kingdom			
Funding programme	European Union's Horizon 2020 Grant agreement 727494			
Duration	2016.10.01 – 2021.09.30			
Total budget	3,585,375 euros			
Consortium^a	5 partners, 3 countries			
	IFAH-EUROPE (BE) OIE (FR)	BBSRC (UK)	CABI (UK)	DEFRA (UK)
Objectives	<p>The overall objective of the Secretariat for the International Research Consortium on Animal Health (SIRCAH) is to facilitate the STAR-IDAZ International Research Consortium on Animal Health (STAR-IDAZ IRC) achieving its objectives by establishing a secretariat to provide organisational and communication support to the STAR-IDAZ IRC and its various members and assisting with the development of focused research roadmaps</p> <p>The specific objectives of SIRCAH are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engaging with STAR-IDAZ IRC and the wider research and stakeholder community, building confidence in and support for the STAR-IDAZ IRC objectives and activities. - Organising meetings of the STAR-IDAZ IRC Executive Committee, Scientific Committee and working groups of researchers on priority topics. - Maintaining the STAR-IDAZ website and databases and keeping all members updated. - Providing secretarial support for STAR-IDAZ IRC. - Assisting the Scientific Committee and Working Groups in organising research gap analysis and development of roadmaps to help with the alignment of research programmes. - Conducting, upon request, the preparation of any documents required by the STAR-IDAZ IRC committees and working groups, including bibliographic searches and organising literature reviews. - Collecting and disseminating pertinent information and results to the researchers funded by STAR-IDAZ IRC members. - Monitoring progress towards achieving the goals of STAR-IDAZ IRC. 			

^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP
Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance (JPIAMR)				
Acronym	JPIAMR				
Website	www.jpiamr.eu				
Coordinator's name	Mats Ulfendahl				
Contact details	secretariat.jpiamr@vr.se ; mats.ulfendahl@ki.se				
Coordinator's Institution	Swedish Research Council in Stockholm (Sweden)				
Funding programme	European Union				
Duration	Ongoing from 2011				
Total budget	65 M Euros				
Consortium^a	27 countries				
	Argentina Belgium Canada Czech Republic Denmark Egypt United Kingdom	Estonia Finland France Germany Greece Ireland Israel	Italy India Japan The Netherlands Norway Poland	Romania South Africa Spain Sweden Switzerland Turkey	
Objectives	<p>The mission for JPIAMR is to join forces across nations by leading the alignment, coordination, and support to Antimicrobial Resistance One Health collaborative research and global policy activities".</p> <p>The overarching major goals are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To align national and international research programmes. - To support and coordinate transformative research. - To support and coordinate the JPIAMR Virtual Research Institute. - To promote innovation and translation of research results. - To bridge the gap between research and policy. 				
Work Packages	<p>Priority topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - THERAPEUTICS: Development of novel antibiotics and alternatives for antibiotics – from basic research to the market. - DIAGNOSTICS: Design strategies to improve treatment and prevention of infections by developing new diagnostics. - SURVEILLANCE: Implementation of a publicly funded global antibiotic resistance surveillance program. - TRANSMISSION: Transmission dynamics. - ENVIRONMENT: The role of the environment and sewage as a source for the emergence and spread of antimicrobial resistance. <p>INTERVENTIONS: Designing and testing interventions to prevent acquisition, transmission and infection caused by antibiotic-resistant bacteria.</p>				

^a OHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP
Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	European Joint Action on antimicrobial resistance and associated interactions			
Acronym	JAMRAI			
Website	https://eu-jamrai.eu/			
Coordinator's name	Marie Cecile Ploy			
Contact details	Marie-cecile.ploy@unilim.fr			
Coordinator's Institution	French National Institute of Health and Medical Research (INSERM), France			
Funding programme	European Union Grant Agreement 761296			
Duration	2017.09.01 – 2020.08.31			
Total budget	4,178,162.75 euros			
Consortium^a	44 partners; 22 countries			
	GOG (AT) FPS HFCSE (BE) NCIPD (BG) NIPH (CZ) RKI (DE) SSI (DK) TA (EE) AEMPS (ES) GENCAT (ES) CSGIB (ES) DGPIFAC/FFIS/SMS (ES)	FMS (ES) SAS/FISEVI/IBIS (ES) ISCIII (ES) SERMAS (ES) ANSES (FR) INSERM (FR) MoH (FR) HCDCP (GR) ESDY-NSPH (GR) 7HRC (GR) CIPH (HR)	UNIFG (IT) ISS (IT) LSMULKK (LT) VULSK (LT) HI (LT) NVSC (LT) PSKUS (LV) VWS (NL) HdiR (NO) FHI (NO) NVI (NO)	NMI (PL) DGS (PT) UMPIH (RO) FOHM (SE) SOS (SE) SBA (SE) NFA (SE) SVA (SE) SRC (SE) UAS (SE) NIJZ (SI)
Objectives	<p>The overarching objective of EU-JAMRAI is to support European Union Member States, develop and implement effective One Health policies to combat Antimicrobial Resistance and reduce Healthcare-Associated Infections. Through appropriate involvement of each group in the different planned actions, the Joint Action will strengthen existing public health policies both at national and European level and contribute to achieving the objectives of the WHO Global Action Plan on AMR, the Council Conclusions on AMR and the EU Action Plan on AMR.</p> <p>General Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To identify and test evidence-based measures to address AMR and HCAI in different contexts and provide recommendations to policymakers. - To bring together different networks of policymakers, experts and organisations working on AMR and HCAI. - To promote: The One Health approach; One Health in all policies concept; and Health in all policies concept. - To produce concrete recommendations and promote awareness and commitment by governments and stakeholders for a European contribution to international initiatives. 			
Work Packages	<p>WP1. Management.</p> <p>WP2. Dissemination.</p>			

	<p>WP3. Evaluation.</p> <p>WP4. Integration in National Policies and sustainability.</p> <p>WP5. Implementation of One Health national strategies and National Action Plans for AMR.</p> <p>WP6. Policies for prevention of HCAI and their implementation.</p> <p>WP7. Appropriate use of antimicrobials in human and in animals.</p> <p>WP8. Awareness raising and communication.</p> <p>WP9. Prioritizing and implementing research and innovation for public health needs.</p>
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^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP
Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Efficient response to highly dangerous and emerging pathogens at EU level			
Acronym	EMERGE			
Website	www.emerge.rki.eu			
Coordinator's name	Roland Grunow			
Contact details	grunowR@rki.de			
Coordinator's Institution	Robert Koch-Institute (RKI), Germany			
Funding programme	EU funded Joint Action (JA), Consumers, Health, Agriculture and Food Executive Agency (CHAFAEA). Grant agreement 677066			
Duration	2015.06.01 – 2018.05.31			
Total budget	3,499,873 euros			
Consortium^a	33 partners, 22 countries			
	AGES (AT) CODA-CERVA (BE) NCIPD (BG) SUJCHBO (CZ) RKI (DE) BwIM (DE) FLI (DE) UMR (DE)	BNITM (DE) DTU (DK) TA (EE) BIOEF (ES) ISCIII (ES) THL (FI) INSERM (FR) DGA (FR)	AUT (GR) HZJZ (HR) NCE (HU) INMI (IT) ISS (IT) IZSLER (IT) NVSPL (LT) RIVM (NL)	ERASMUS MC (NL) NIPH (NO) NVI (NO) NIPH-NIH (PL) NVRI (PL) INSA (PT) INC (RO) FoHM (SE) PHE (UK)
Objectives	EMERGE aims to ensure efficient response to serious emergent and re-emergent cross-border events by reinforcing the existing EU network of BSL-3 and BSL-4 laboratories which are already active in the field of identification of dangerous bacterial and viral human pathogens. The JA contributes to provide an integrated European laboratory infrastructure and strategy to protect European citizens against exposure to a panel of globally recognized high threat bacteria and viruses. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Networking of networks for laboratory response establishing and strengthening the cooperation between networks. - Improving capabilities for rapid laboratory diagnosis of new or emerging pathogens (e.g. sample sharing) - Quality Assurance for laboratory diagnostics by External Quality Assurance Exercises (EQAE). - Training on diagnostics and biorisk management. - All activities are planned for a direct laboratory response in relevant outbreak situations and for improvement of laboratory preparedness in interepidemic phases. 			
Work Packages	WP1. Coordination of the Joint Action. WP2. Dissemination of the Joint Action activities. WP3. Evaluation of the Joint Action. WP4. Networking of networks for laboratory response. WP5. Rapid capabilities for diagnoses. WP6. Quality assurance of laboratory Diagnostics.			

	WP7. Training on diagnostics and biorisk management.
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^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP
Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	European Virus Archive goes Global			
Acronym	EvaG			
Website	https://www.european-virus-archive.com/			
Coordinator's name	Jean-Louis Romette			
Contact details	EVAg-Coordination@european-virus-archive.com			
Coordinator's Institution	Universite d' Aix Marseille (AMU), France			
Funding programme	European Union's Horizon 2020 Grant agreement 653316			
Duration	2015.04.01 – 2019.03.01			
Total budget	12,168,054.68 euros			
Consortium^a	25 Partners, 12 countries			
	CSIRO AAHL (AU) UNIBAS (CH) WIC (CN) BNI (DE) UKB (DE) RKI (DE)	FLI (DE) AMU (FR) FMER (FR) INSERM (FR) IP (FR) INMI (IT)	EMC (NL) LUMC (NL) IPVE (RU) RII (RU) MECHNIKOV RIVS (RU) FOHM (SE)	UL (SI) IVSAS (SK) APHA (UK) PHE (UK) TPI (UK) ARC OVI (ZA) NICD NHLS (ZA)
Objectives	<p>The major objective is to meet the needs of scientists worldwide by generating a carefully authenticated human/animal virus collection that is larger than any existing repository, and which is readily available to all laboratories that meet approved ethical, safety and security standards.</p> <p>EVAg is a non-profit organisation dedicated to the characterisation, conservation, production, distribution and characterisation of biological materials in the field of virology.</p> <p>The EVAg consortium also ensures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - that materials are supplied non-profitably or at cost to all bona fide applicants, - that biosafety and security measures are appropriately addressed by the supplying and recipient labs, - that the available materials meet the highest scientific standards in terms of quality and characterization, - that the property of the provided materials remains with the originators. <p>One of the key features of this project will be the implementation of platforms dedicated to providing access to the entire EVAg resource, including virus discovery techniques, sequencing and derived material production for diagnostic applications.</p>			
Work Packages	NA			

^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP
Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Platform for European Preparedness Against (Re-)emerging Epidemics			
Acronym	PREPARE		Platform for European Preparedness Against (Re-)emerging Epidemics	
Website	http://www.prepare-europe.eu/			
Coordinator's name	Herman Goossens			
Contact details	herman.goossens@uza.be			
Coordinator's Institution	Univesity of Antwerp (UAntwerp), Belgium			
Funding programme	European Union's FP7-HEALTH Grant agreement 602525			
Duration	2014.02.01 – 2019.01.31			
Total budget	31,130,188.06 euros			
Consortium^a	26 partners, 14 countries			
	UWA (AU) UAntwerp (BE) Biocartis (BE) Janssen (BE) ESWI (BE) ERS (CH) CAPNETZ (DE)	Biomax (DE) UBonn (DE) SERGAS (ES) HLA-MED (FR) BioMerieux (FR) IP (FR) USplit (HR)	UCD (IE) PENTA (IT) Erasmus MC (NL) AMC (NL) UMC Utrecht (NL) WONCA (WHO) ESCMID (SE)	BERRY (UK) CU (UK) Imperial College (UK) OX (UK) NHS (UK)
Objectives	<p>PREPARE establishes a European clinical research framework for harmonised large-scale clinical research studies on infectious diseases, prepared to rapidly respond to any severe infectious disease outbreak, providing real-time evidence for clinical management of patients and for informing public health responses.</p> <p>The European clinical research framework of PREPARE consists of three interconnected platforms (PATHOS, PRACTICE and PREDICT), supported by a common ICT infrastructure (CRISP) and strengthened by a comprehensive training and education effort (CREATE).</p>			
Work Packages	<p>WP1. EARL: Ethical, Administrative, Regulatory And Logistical Solutions.</p> <p>WP2. PRIME: Clinical protocols and guidelines for Id Management in Europe.</p> <p>WP3. PRACTICE A: Observational Study.</p> <p>WP4. PRACTICE B: Interventional Trial Influenza-Like-Illness In Primary Care.</p> <p>WP5. PRACTICE C: Adaptative randomised trial Severe Acute Respiratory Infection.</p> <p>WP6. PATHOS: European harmonised large scale patient-oriented pathogenesis research studies in response to severe infectious disease outbreaks.</p> <p>WP7. PREDICT: European harmonised large scale patient-oriented pathogenesis research studies in response to severe infectious disease outbreaks.</p> <p>WP8. CRISP: Clinical Research Information Sharing Platform.</p> <p>WP9. CREATE: Clinical Research Education and Training In Europe.</p> <p>WP11. COCO: Consortium Coordination.</p>			

^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	Veterinary Biocontained facility Network for excellence in animal infectious disease research and experimentation							
Acronym	VetBioNet							
Website	http://www.vetbionet.eu/							
Coordinator's name	Frederic Lantier							
Contact details	frederic.lantier@inra.fr							
Coordinator's Institution	Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique (INRA), France							
Funding programme	European Union's Horizon 2020 Grant agreement 731014							
Duration	2017.03.01 – 2022.02.28							
Total budget	10,017,890.50 euros							
Consortium ^a	27 partners, 14 countries							
	AAHL (AUS) EDI-IVI (CH) FLI (DE) ISX (DE) LEICA (DE) AU (DK) INIA (ES)	IRTA (ES) INGENASA (ES) INRA (FR) ANSES (FR) NUID-UCD (IE) IZSve (IT) EAAP (IT)	ILRI (KEN) WBVR (NL) Erasmus MC (NL) Noldus (NL) PIWET (PL) TPI (UK) APHA (UK)	MRI (UK) MS (UK) UEDIN (UK) UNOTT (UK) EpiBio (UK) VAL (UK)				
Objectives	<p>VetBioNet seeks to complement and strengthen the present European capacity and competence to meet the challenges of (re)emerging infectious diseases by establishing a comprehensive network of pre-eminent European high-containment (BSL3) infrastructures, international organisations, and industry partners that is dedicated to advance research on epizootic and zoonotic diseases and to promote technological developments.</p> <p>To reach this overall objective VetBioNet will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote and facilitate Transnational Access (TNA) to the infrastructure resources of the network, including BSL3 animal experimental facilities and laboratories, technological platforms, and sample collections. - Promote technological development by involving private partners in the integrating activities of the network and by providing a communication platform for bidirectional exchange with industry stakeholders (Stakeholder Platform). - Enhance the preparedness of the major European BSL3 research infrastructures to accelerate the response to (re)emerging epizootic and zoonotic threats by sharing capacities beyond the infrastructures. - Harmonise Best Practices and promote the use of global standards in European BSL3 infrastructures. - Forge cooperative relationships with non-European BSL3 infrastructures, research institutes, industrial partners, international organisations, and policy makers. - Ensure high ethical standards and clarify the social impact of VetBioNet research 							

	<p>work.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop and implement a Sustainability Plan for the network to continue beyond the five-year term of funding. - Carry out Joint Research Activities (JRAs) designed to improve the scientific and technological standards of the integrated services provided by the network infrastructures.
<p>Work Packages</p>	<p>WPs 1-6. Networking Activities: WP1. Transnational Access Management; WP2. Development of a Preparedness Plan to enhance the preparedness of the VetBioNet BSL3 research infrastructures to respond to emerging infectious disease threats; WP3. Harmonisation of Best Practices and Biosafety/security standards; WP4. Ethical standards and social impact of VetBioNet research work; WP5. Dissemination, Data Management, and Training opportunities; WP6. Development and implementation of a Sustainability Plan.</p> <p>WPs 7-9. Joint Research Activities: WP7. Establishing novel and/or optimised infection models; WP8. Developing and/or validating novel analytical tools; WP9. Developing and/or validating novel telemetric or imaging tools.</p> <p>WP10. Project Management.</p> <p>WPs 11-31. Transnational Access Activities: to provide direct access to the partners' proprietary BSL3 infrastructures and technological platforms as well as remote access to the partners' sample collections, cell lines, immunological reagents, and animals</p>

^a OHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP
Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	European Network Of CBRN Training Centers		
Acronym	eNOTICE		
Website	https://www.h2020-enotice.eu/		
Coordinator's name	Olga Vybornova		
Contact details	info@h2020-enotice.eu		
Coordinator's Institution	Universite Catholique de Louvain (UCL), Belgium		
Funding programme	European Union's Horizon 2020 Grant agreement 740521		
Duration	2017.09.01 – 2022.08.31		
Total budget	3,587,422.50 euros		
Consortium^a	13 partners, 9 countries		
	UCL (BE) VESTA (BE) JCBRND COE (CZ) FDDO (DE)	UPB (DE) SDIS 77 (FR) ARMINES (FR) UNITOV (IT)	WSU (PO) CNBOP-PIB (PO) UMU (SE)
Objectives	<p>The overall goal of the eNOTICE project is to build a dynamic, functional and sustainable pan European network of CBRN (Chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear) training, testing and demonstration centres aiming at enhancing CBRN training capacity for improved preparedness and incident response through increased collaboration between CBRN training centres and practitioners' needs-driven CBRN innovation and research.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establishing a Framework for European network of CBRN TC, testing and demonstration sites. - Connect Training Centers: establish a web based information and communication platform to provide, share and disseminate information during and after the project. - Optimize Resources: set up an operational transactional network for optimising investments by pooling and sharing resources, expertise, and effective practices, by organising joint activities between the eNOTICE network members and external partners, and by liaising with other networks of CBRN stakeholders. 		
Work Packages	<p>WP2. Framework for a sustainable European CBRN TC network.</p> <p>WP3. Information and communication platform and dissemination.</p> <p>WP4. Integration, optimization and joint activities.</p> <p>WP5. Project management and quality monitoring.</p>		

^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

Project/Initiative Information Sheet

Oneh Health EJP
Grant Agreement number 773830

Name project/initiative	European Union Chemical Biological Radiological and Nuclear Risk Mitigation Centres of Excellence Initiative				
Acronym	EU CBRN CoE				
Website	http://www.cbrn-coe.eu/				
Coordinator's name Contact details Coordinator's Institution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - European Commission Development and Cooperation - EuropeAid (DEVCO); Mr Tristan Simonart; tristan.simonart@ec.europa.eu; http://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/ - European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC); Mr Michael Thornton; michael.thornton@jrc.ec.europa.eu; https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/ - European External Action Service (EEAS); Mr Bruno Dupré; bruno.dupre@eeas.europa.eu; http://www.eeas.europa.eu/ - United Nations Interregional Crime and Justice Research Institute (UNICRI); Ms Marian de Bruijn; debruijn@unicri.it; http://www.unicri.it/ 				
Funding programme	European Union Instrument Contributing to Security and Peace (IcSP).				
Duration	2010.01.01 – 2020.12.31				
Total budget	250,000,000 euros				
Consortium^a	59 countries (membership is voluntary) <table border="0" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> African Atlantic Façade (9 countries) North Africa and Sahel (7 countries) Middle East (3 countries) South East and Eastern Europe (10 countries) </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> Eastern and Central Africa (11 countries) Gulf Cooperation Council Countries (4 countries) Central Asia (6 countries) South East Asia (10 countries) </td> </tr> </table>			African Atlantic Façade (9 countries) North Africa and Sahel (7 countries) Middle East (3 countries) South East and Eastern Europe (10 countries)	Eastern and Central Africa (11 countries) Gulf Cooperation Council Countries (4 countries) Central Asia (6 countries) South East Asia (10 countries)
African Atlantic Façade (9 countries) North Africa and Sahel (7 countries) Middle East (3 countries) South East and Eastern Europe (10 countries)	Eastern and Central Africa (11 countries) Gulf Cooperation Council Countries (4 countries) Central Asia (6 countries) South East Asia (10 countries)				
Objectives	<p>The EU CBRN CoE was launched in response to the need to strengthen the institutional capacity of countries outside the European Union to mitigate CBRN risks.</p> <p>The CoE aims to strengthen regional security by increasing local ownership, local expertise and long-term sustainability. The CoE is centred around a worldwide network of local experts and collaborating partners. The CoE aims to strengthen regional security by increasing local ownership, local expertise and by ensuring long-term sustainability through this dynamic network that continues to evolve.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create an international network of CBRN expertise. - Facilitate the cooperation process between network members. - Support Partner Countries in creating their National CBRN Teams. - Establish Regional Secretariats to Foster regional cooperation. - Develop methodology and guidelines. 				

^aOHEJP partners in bold; Alphabetical order by country (acronym)

APPENDIX T: Descriptions and scoring levels of the criteria used in the MCDA for the research topics

C1: Inclusion of the human, animal and environmental components

This criterion relates to the level of “One Health-ness” of the research topic. Three components are distinguished: humans, animals and the environment. The more components can be included under a given research topic, the greater its level of One Health-ness is. To consider a component as being included, its inclusion should extend beyond general considerations: it should put a strong focus on the interaction between components. For example: taking only air samples does not qualify for the environmental component to be considered as included. Taking air samples in support of developing models to simulate airborne transmission from animals to humans and vice versa does qualify for the environmental component to be considered as included. If, for instance, in addition to modelling airborne transmission, the infection dynamics in an animal reservoir(s) and in humans are needed to be studied to address the topic, then the research topic can be considered to include all three components.

Criterion levels and decision rules:

Low: the research topic focuses mostly on one component, or on multiple components without a clear focus on their interaction

Medium: the research topic involves two components to be addressed, including the transmission and/or interactions between these two components

High: the research topic considers all three components to be addressed, including transmission and/or interactions between all these three components

C2: Potential *direct* impact to decrease disease and/or economic burden for humans and animals

This criterion reflects the expectations regarding *direct* effects of the research results under the topic on minimizing the burden (*i.e.*, health losses and/or economic losses) due to the veterinary and/or public health issue(s) under study. A direct impact is considered here as achievable when outputs from project activities under the research topic lead to directly implementable actions. Such outputs include, for instance, the development of directly applicable intervention measures, reductions of the economic impact of trade bans, and direct use of vaccines. For both components, *i.e.*, humans or animals, you should assess whether project results under the topic will likely have a direct none-to-low or medium-to-high value. The criteria selection is done according to this assessment as detailed below.

		Burden related to humans	
		None-to-low	Medium-to-high
Burden related to animals	None-to-low	1	2
	Medium-to-high	2	3

Criterion levels and decision rules:

Low: score 1

Medium: score 2

High: score 3

C3: Potential *indirect* impact to decrease the disease and economic burden for humans and animals

This criterion reflects the expectations regarding *indirect* effects of the topic results on minimizing the burden

(i.e., health losses and/or economic losses) due to the veterinary and/or public health issue(s) under study. An indirect impact means here that actions cannot be taken directly when needed and further steps are needed before implementation. Indirect effects include, for instance, diagnostic test development, creation of networks/platforms, and the generation of knowledge that supports the development of intervention measures, but that still needs further studies before implementation. For both components, i.e., humans or animals, you should assess whether project results are expected to have a none-to-low or medium-to-high value on the improvement of human and animal health. The criteria selection is done according to this assessment as detailed below.

		Burden related to humans	
		None-to-low	Medium-to-high
Burden related to animals	None-to-low	1	2
	Medium-to-high	2	3

Criterion levels and decision rules:

Low: score 1

Medium: score 2

High: score 3

C4: Number of stakeholders from whom the research needs are addressed

Stakeholders' needs are an important attribute to consider in the second round of prioritization. These needs are countable, as a certain number of similar needs are identified from the various stakeholders. The more needs that are addressed by a given research topic, the higher the criterion score will be. Each research need counts as one, so if two stakeholders express the same need and it is likely to be addressed by a research topic, then this counts as two needs being addressed. This leads to an implicit weighting of the research needs according to importance, where needs that are mentioned by multiple stakeholders are considered to be more important than research needs mentioned one time.

Criterion levels and decision rules:

Stakeholder	Need 1	Need 2	Need 3	Need 4	Need ...	Need n
EFSA	AAA	BBB	CCC	-
ECDC	BBB	CCC	DDD	EEE
DG Santé	BBB	DDD	FFF	GGG

No stakeholder needs: the research topic addresses no stakeholders' needs.

1 or 2: the research topic addresses 1 or 2 stakeholders' needs. *E.g.*, a topic addressing only need CCC, or a topic addressing needs AAA and EEE simultaneously.

3 or more: the research topic addresses 3 or more stakeholders' needs. *E.g.*, a topic addressing only need BBB, or a project addressing needs CCC and DDD simultaneously.

C5: Foreseen strengthening of alignment between partners

This criterion covers the contribution of research topics to the aim of EJP to align the scientific activities of institutes in different countries. Alignment is defined as the harmonization of approaches, methodologies, tools, procedures and/or agendas, so that every partner would do the same in response to a certain threat or circumstance. Alignment is thus focused more on the planning phase, detailing *what* activities to carry out by

coordinating or harmonizing research, use of methods and techniques, etc., between partner institutes. This criterion deals especially with the contribution to improving the alignment that research topics can make among partner institutes within EJPOH. As example: a project focusing on salmonella serotyping might lead to less improvements in alignment (almost all partners already do the same) compared to a topic focused on WGS-surveillance (little alignment to date).

Criterion levels and decision rules:

Low: the research topic does not lead to improved alignment because the topic is not focused on improving alignment and/or alignment is already well established.

Medium: some alignment has already been established in the past, and this research topic adds something to further improvement of this alignment.

High: there has been no or little alignment established in the past and the research to be carried out within the topic has the potential to improve the alignment substantially.

C6: Strategic interactions with other ongoing or completed EU projects and/or initiatives

A research topic that can build on the output of other ongoing studies or initiatives is seen as an advantageous topic. The discrimination among research topics depends on the possibility of strategic interactions and the beneficiaries of the interactions (one-way or bidirectional), as explained in the decision rules below.

Criterion levels and decision rules:

No strategic interaction: the research topic cannot align with, or is not based on, ongoing or completed EU projects or initiatives.

Little strategic interaction: the research topic can benefit from output of ongoing or completed research or initiatives, for instance by using samples, databases or protocols. The interaction is mostly one-way.

Large strategic interactions: the research topic has the ability to interact with ongoing EU projects/initiatives, whereby both can benefit from each other. The interaction is predominantly two-way.

C7: The level of innovation that a research topic enables

EJP One Health aims for innovative research and therefore a research topic that enables innovative research is seen as an advantageous topic. Although the level of innovation is difficult to assess beforehand, some topics are more likely to enable innovative research than others. This criterion is meant to distinguish the set of research topics to prioritize along this theme.

Criterion levels and decision rules:

No innovation: the research topic does not enable or trigger innovative research components.

Moderate innovation: the research topic creates some opportunities for innovative research components. This can be seen as a 'standard', or baseline level of innovation under research topics.

Large innovation: the research topic highly likely triggers innovative research components to be considered.

APPENDIX U: Descriptions and scoring levels of the criteria used in the MCDA for the integrative topics

ITC1: Number of needs expressed by One Health EJP partners that are addressed

Partners have identified areas that would need improvement in the joint response capacity in their view. These needs are countable, because a certain number of needs are identified from the various partners. Each expressed need counts as one, so if two partners express the same need and it is likely to be addressed by an integrative activity, then this counts as two needs being addressed. All the needs that have been expressed by partners have been summarized by integrative activity and graphically displayed in the source document 'Outcome of partner consultation regarding needs for integrative projects'. The number behind the bars can be used to count the number of partner needs. That document also contains WordClouds showing the original contributions from partners that defines the integrative activity. These WordClouds can be used to get an impression of where the needs expressed under each activity have their focus.

<10 needs addressed: the integrative activity addresses up to 10 partner needs.

10-19 needs addressed: the integrative activity addresses between 10 and 19 partner needs.

≥20 needs addressed: the integrative activity addresses 20 or more partner needs.

ITC2: Number of needs expressed by stakeholders that are addressed

Similar to the partners, stakeholders have identified areas that would need improvement in the joint response capacity in their view. These needs are countable, because a certain number of needs are identified from the various stakeholders. Each expressed need counts as one, so if two stakeholders express the same need and it is likely to be addressed by an integrative activity, then this counts as two needs being expressed. This leads to an implicit weighting of the needs according to importance, because needs that are mentioned by multiple stakeholders are considered to be more important than research needs mentioned one time.

Criterion levels and decision rules:

Stakeholder	Need 1	Need 2	Need 3	Need 4
A	AAA	BBB	CCC	-
B	BBB	CCC	DDD	EEE
...	BBB	DDD	FFF	GGG

No needs addressed: the integrative activity address no stakeholders' needs.

1 or 2 needs addressed: the integrative activity addresses 1 or 2 stakeholders' needs. *E.g.*, an activity addressing only need CCC in the exemplary table above (same need mentioned by 2 stakeholders), or an integrative activity addressing simultaneously needs AAA (stakeholders A's need) and EEE (stakeholders B's need).

3 or more needs addressed: the integrative activity addresses 3 or more stakeholders' needs. *E.g.*, an activity addressing only need BBB (same need mentioned by 3 stakeholders), or an activity addressing simultaneously needs CCC (mentioned by 2 stakeholders) and DDD (mentioned by 2 stakeholders).

ITC3: Recurrence of the issue addressed by the integrative activity across domains

This criterion relates to the breadth of the integrative activity regarding the One Health EJP domains (i.e., foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats). If an integrative activity improves or solves an issue that is shared by several domains, then this is seen as an advantage: the more domains that are

facing the challenge that is addressed, the higher the importance of an integrative activity in this prioritization. In terms of the OH-EJP matrix, with the domains in columns and themes in the rows, this would be analogous to an integration across the horizontal-axis of that matrix, so across the domains.

Criterion levels and decision rules:

Low: The issue that is tackled by the integrative activity mostly exists in one domain.

Medium: The issue that is tackled by the integrative activity is shared by two of the three domains .

High: The issue that is tackled by the integrative activity is shared by all of the domains.

ITC4: Integration along the axis of the ‘prevention, detection and response’-chain

Integration along the axis from detection to response is focused on seamless interaction between different fields of expertise along the chain. Different areas of this chain include, e.g.:

- Design and implementation of surveillance activities
- Laboratory methods and analyses
- Reference materials and data
- Interpretation of surveillance data
- Communication of surveillance data
- Action (prevention and response)

This chain is largely reflected in the OHEJP strategy matrix by the different themes.

As an example: proper integration would mean that relevant zoonotic threats can be detected in veterinary surveillance, are passed on to public health authorities seamlessly, interpreted appropriately, evoking a coordinated response at relevant points in the transmission chain while minimizing public unrest through an effective communication strategy. The potential for integration along the vertical axis is scored according to the foreseen number of areas in the chain that are involved. Although the ‘prevention, detection and response’-chain is not entirely compatible with the OH-EJP matrix, criterion ITC4 relates more to an integration along the vertical-axis of that matrix than the horizontal axis, so across the themes.

Criterion levels and decision rules:

Low: The integrative activity has its main focus on one area of the chain.

Medium: The integrative activity has its main focus on two areas of the chain.

High: The integrative activity has its main focus on three or more areas of the chain.

ITC5: Effects of the integrative activity on the joint response capacity

This criterion focuses on the expected effects of the integrative activity on the joint response capacity. It deals with the impact of bottlenecks or leverage points on the system as a whole. Of interest for assessing bottlenecks is the magnitude of prevented negative effects of continuing with the current mode of operation (e.g. preventing unnecessary costs due to inefficiencies that currently exist), and for leverage points it is the magnitude of the positive effects that result from addressing the activity (e.g., improved animal or human health or positive effects in other parts of the response system that were not aimed at primarily). An example of a bottleneck is all types of constraints to data sharing, which results in delay in communication and impaired joint situation awareness. Similarly, a leverage point could be the sharing of a significant innovation used in one country or one sector to the larger consortium.

Criterion levels and decision rules

Low: The integrative activity leads to only minor impact on reducing negative effects and improving positive

effects.

Medium: The integrative activity leads to moderate impact on reducing negative effects and/or improving positive effects.

High: The integrative activity leads to large impact on reducing negative effects and/or improving positive effects.

ITC6: Strategic interactions with other ongoing or completed EU projects and/or initiatives

An integrative activity that can build on the output of other ongoing studies or initiatives is seen as an advantageous activity. The discrimination among integrative activities depends on the possibility of strategic interactions and the beneficiaries of the interactions (i.e., one-way or bidirectional), as explained in the decision rules below.

Criterion levels and decision rules:

No strategic interaction: the integrative activity cannot align with, or is not based on, ongoing or completed EU projects or initiatives.

Little strategic interaction: the integrative activity can benefit from output of ongoing or completed research or initiatives, for instance by using samples, databases or protocols. The interaction is mostly one-way.

Large strategic interactions: the integrative activity has the ability to interact with ongoing EU projects/initiatives, whereby both can benefit from each other. The interaction is predominantly two-way.

APPENDIX Z: Weights of the MCDA-criteria for research and integrative topics based on the PMT members' assessment

Criterion (research topics)	Weight
Inclusion of the human, animal and environmental components	0.17
Potential direct impact to decrease disease and/or economic burden for humans and animals	0.18
Potential indirect impact to decrease the disease and economic burden for humans and animals	0.15
Number of stakeholders from whom the research needs are addressed	0.14
Foreseen strengthening of alignment between partners	0.14
Strategic interactions with other ongoing or completed EU projects and/or initiatives	0.10
The level of innovation that a research topic enables	0.12

Criterion (integrative topics)	Weight
Number of needs expressed by One Health EJP partners that are addressed	0.16
Number of needs expressed by stakeholders that are addressed	0.17
Recurrence of the issue addressed by the integrative topic across domains	0.17
Integration along the axis of the 'prevention, detection and response'-chain	0.17
Effects of the integrative topic on the joint response capacity	0.18
Strategic interactions with other ongoing or completed EU projects and/or initiatives	0.14